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Deliverable 6.3

Integration of *in silico* and *in vitro* data in PBPK modeling for risk assessment of food- and non-food-borne chemicals using the Euromix toolbox

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ABSTRACT

Physiologically-based toxicokinetic (PTPK) models are important tools for *in vitro* to *in vivo* or inter-species extrapolations in health risk assessment of food-borne and non-food borne chemicals. We present here the results obtained on nine chemicals (three endocrine disrupters, three liver steatosis inducers, and three developmental toxicants) when increasingly complex levels of parametrization are applied a generic PBPK model implemented in the Euromix toolbox, MCRA 9. At the first stage high-throughput parameter estimates were used. In a second stage we introduced parameter values estimated using other QSAR models and then combined the latter with parameters from *in vitro* methods. The results show that parameterisation plays a capital role in the output of the PBPK model, and that in many cases of chronic exposure, the PBPK model can be summarized by an external to internal dose factor, and that interspecies concentration factors can be used to perform interspecies extrapolation. We finally discuss the implementation and use of the model in the MCRA risk assessment platform.

INTRODUCTION

The EuroMix toolbox implemented in the Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) platform allows users to simulate exposures of populations of individuals to food-borne chemicals [1]. The platform allows users to integrate exposure assessments, *in vitro* dose-response data and knowledge on Adverse Outcome Pathways into risk assessment. *In vitro* dose-response relationships quantify responses at the cell level as a function of the internal dose at tissue level. The kinetic module included in the MCRA risk assessment platform allows users to make use of *in vitro* dose-response relationship by converting internal doses at the target organ into human exposure doses, and thus performing *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation (IVIVE). One of the main underlying kinetic models is a Physiologically-Based Toxicokinetic (PBTK) model.

PBPK models represent the organism as a set of compartments linked together by the bloodstream. Following a given chemical exposure (acute or chronic), the time-courses of the chemical inside each compartment can be predicted. The PBPK model developed in the COSMOS FP7 European project is a generic model, designed to be well-suited for a wide range of chemicals. The physiological parameters used in a PBPK model are specific to a given species and the structure may also be specific in some regards. The COSMOS model has been adapted to both humans and rats with the same underlying structure. In the case responses have been observed *in vivo* at the organ or tissue level in rats, using both rat and human PBPK models refines the interspecies extrapolation.

Building a PBPK model requires gathering a considerable amount of data which can be categorized in three groups, namely, the model structure, which refers to the arrangement of tissues and organs included in the model; the system's data (physiological, anatomical, biochemical data); and chemical-specific data (physicochemical). Chemical-specific data can be collected from a variety of sources, using default values, *in vivo* measurements, *in vitro* cell-based assays, or *in silico* predictions. The

increasing amount of high-throughput *in vitro* data, in particular on metabolism and chemical binding, available nowadays encourages the use of kinetic models as a screening approach.

In this paper we compare various levels of refinement in PBPK model building, using QSAR models and *in vitro* data, and show how these models can be used in cumulative risk assessment. Nine chemicals are used as examples; these chemicals induce steatosis (Imazalil, Thiacloprid, and Clothianidin), endocrine effects (Flutamide, Linuron, and Dienestrol), or cranio-facial malformations (Cyproconazole, Triadimefon, and Valproic acid).

METHODS

PBPK model

Model description

In the framework of the EU project COSMOS (part of the SEURAT-1 cluster, <http://www.cosmostox.eu/> [2,3]), INERIS and JRC developed a generic PBPK model. It is available in *GNU MCSim*, in *R*, and also online in the MCRA platform. In Euromix, we updated it to improve the dermal absorption model based on the SEURAT piperonyl butoxide model, to scale all partition coefficients to the fat partition coefficient, and to allow more exposure patterns: the model used in Euromix is version 6 of the generic PBPK model developed at INERIS in the framework of COSMOS [2] (Figure 1). The model describes the distribution of chemicals in venous blood, arterial blood, adipose tissues, poorly perfused tissues (muscles), gut lumen, liver, richly perfused tissues (other viscera), and skin. Each of those is described as a compartment (homogeneous virtual volume) in which distribution is instantaneous and limited only by the incoming blood flow or rate of entry in the compartment [4]. Exposure can occur through the dermal route, ingestion or inhalation. The absorbed molecules can be excreted to urine, exhaled through the lung, or metabolized in liver.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the “COSMOS” PBPK model implemented in the MCRA platform.

The model is coded as a set of ordinary differential equations. There is one such equation per time-dependent chemical quantity of the model (so-called state variables). There are 13 state variables in the model: the quantity of chemical in venous blood (Q_{ven}), in arterial blood (Q_{art}), in adipose tissues (Q_{fat}), in poorly perfused tissues (Q_p), in well perfused tissues (Q_r), in liver (Q_{liv}), in unexposed skin ($Q_{s,u}$), in exposed skin ($Q_{s,e}$), in the stratum corneum of unexposed skin ($Q_{sc,u}$), in exposed stratum corneum ($Q_{sc,e}$), in gut lumen (Q_{gut}), the quantity excreted to urine (Q_{ex}), and the quantity metabolized (Q_{met}). The model can predict, as a function of time, for given oral, dermal and/or inhalation exposures, all the above quantities and the corresponding concentrations as a function of time. The model equations have been fully documented in Deliverable 4.2. The model can also be used to determine to which extent each exposure route contributes to the kinetics in each compartment

Physiological parameter values

The model contains 14 physiological parameters. To model known correlations between parameter values, or to respect physical constraints in case of Monte Carlo sampling, some of them are scaled prior to solving the differential equations, using proportionality constants called “scaling coefficients”. The scaling equations are also documented in Deliverable 4.2. Default values for physiological scaling coefficients and unscaled parameters for (Wistar) rats (see Table 1) and humans (Table 2) have been collected.

Table 1: Default physiological parameter values or scaling coefficients of the “COSMOS” model proposed in MCRA for Wistar rats.

Parameter	Symbol	Units	Value	References
Body mass	<i>BM</i>	kg	0.3	[5,6]
Body skin surface area	<i>BSA</i>	dm ²	3.64	[7]
<i>Relative tissue volumes</i>				
Fat	<i>scVFat</i>	-	0.073	[5,6]
Richly perfused	<i>scVRich</i>	-	0.100	[5,6]
Liver	<i>scVLiver</i>	-	0.035	[5,6]
Blood	<i>scVBlood</i>	-	0.068	[8]
<i>Relative tissue blood flows</i>				
Fat	<i>scFFat</i>	-	0.0054	[5,6]
Poorly perfused	<i>scFPoor</i>	-	0.100	[5,6]
Liver	<i>scFLiver</i>	-	0.160	[5,6]
Skin	<i>scFSkin</i>	-	0.078	[5,6]
Total blood flow	<i>scFBlood</i>	L/h/kg	18.8	[8]
Alveolar ventilation rate	<i>Falv</i>	L/h	6.35	[6]
Microsomal proteins	<i>mic</i>	mg/g liver	45 ^a	[9]
Stratum corneum thickness	<i>Height_sc</i>	dm	0.0001	[10]
Viable skin thickness	<i>Height_vs</i>	dm	0.0094 ^b	[5,6]

^a This parameter is not used in the model and is just given for reference.

^b Value obtained by dividing the skin volume by the body surface area.

Table 2: Default physiological parameter values or scaling coefficients of the “COSMOS” model proposed in MCRA for humans.

Parameter	Symbol	Units	Value	References
Body mass	<i>BM</i>	kg	57, 75 ^a	[8]
Body skin surface area	<i>BSA</i>	dm ²	190	[10]
<i>Relative tissue volumes</i>				
Fat	<i>scVFat</i>		0.209	[5,6]
Richly perfused	<i>scVRich</i>		0.105	[5,6]
Liver	<i>scVLiver</i>		0.024	[5,6]
Blood	<i>scVBlood</i>		0.068	[8]
<i>Relative tissue blood flows</i>				
Fat	<i>scFFat</i>		0.046	[5,6]
Poorly perfused	<i>scFPoor</i>		0.134	[5,6]
Liver	<i>scFLiver</i>		0.259	[5,6]
Skin	<i>scFSkin</i>		0.054	[5,6]
Total blood flow	<i>scFBlood</i>	L/h/kg	4.8	[8]
Alveolar ventilation rate	<i>Falv</i>	L/h	2220	[6]
Microsomal proteins	<i>mic</i>	mg/g liver	52.5 ^b	[9]
Stratum corneum thickness	<i>Height_sc</i>	dm	0.0001	[10]
Viable skin thickness	<i>Height_vs</i>	dm	0.0122 ^c	[5,6]

^a The first value is for females, the second for males.

^b This parameter is not used in the model and is just given for reference.

^c Value obtained by dividing the skin volume by the body surface area.

Substance-specific parameter values

Chemical-specific parameters were collected for the nine selected chemicals (Three endocrine disruptors: Flutamide, Linuron, and Dienestrol; Three liver steatosis inducers: Imazalil, Thiachloprid, and Clothianidin; Three developmental toxicants: Cyproconazole, Triadimefon, and Valproic acid).

The model contains 15 chemical-dependent parameters (16 parameters if saturable, Michaelis-Menten, metabolism is used). Their scaling coefficients are listed in Table 3.

Table 3: List of chemical-specific parameters and scaling coefficients of the MCRA “COSMOS” model.

Parameter or scaling coefficient	Symbol	Unit
<i>Partition coefficient related</i>		
Blood / air partition coefficient	PC_{Air}	-
Fat/blood partition coefficient	PC_{Fat}	-
Liver/blood partition coefficient	PC_{Liver}	-
Poorly perfused/blood partition coefficient	PC_{Poor}	-
Richly perfused/blood partition coefficient	PC_{Rich}	-
Viable skin/blood partition coefficient	PC_{Skin}	-
Viable skin/blood partition coefficient	$PC_{Skin\ sc}$	-
Unbound fraction in blood	fub	-
Fraction absorbed by gut	$Frac$	-
Oral absorption rate	$kGut$	1/h
Renal excretion rate	Ke	L/h
Linear metabolism flag	<i>Michaelis</i>	- ^a
Maximum metabolic rate	$Vmax$	mmole/h/L liver
Michaelis-Menten constant	Km	mM
Linear metabolic clearance	CLH	L/h
Skin diffusion coefficient	Kp_{sc_vs}	dm/h

^a This indicator variable should be set to zero if metabolism is linear and to one if is saturable. In the first case, CLH should be given a value, in the second case $Vmax$ and Km should be given. If there is no metabolism, *Michaelis* should be set to zero and CLH also.

Chemical-specific parameters can be obtained with *in vivo* measurements (e.g. for partition coefficients), *in vitro* measurements or *in silico*. There was no *in vivo* data available that could be used directly to parameterize the PBTK model. Four types of parameterization, based on *in vitro* and *in silico* methods, were tested to study how the parameter values could affect the predicted internal concentrations. The first three parameterisations are *ab initio* and make use of available pharmacokinetic or toxicokinetic data and *in vitro* experiments carried out specifically in the Euromix project. The fourth parameterization is based on results obtained previously in Euromix, where *in vivo* kinetic data was used to calibrate certain model parameters. The characteristics of the parameterisations are reported in Table 4.

First, QSAR models were used to predict 11 of the 15 chemical-dependent parameters. Secondly, parameters were extracted from the htk R package [11]; these included QSAR estimates and *in vitro* screening test clearances. Finally, additional *in vitro* clearances were added to the QSAR-only parameterization: these values were obtained using hepatocytes during the Euromix project, and, in cases where clearance could not be quantified, the screening values obtained from htk were used.

Table 5,

and Table 12 list the values used for Flutamide, Linuron, Dienestrol, Imazalil, Thioclopid, Clothianidin, Cyproconazole, Triadimefon, and Valproic acid in rats and humans.

Table 4: Characteristics of the four different parameterisations used

Parameterisation	Partition coefficients	Hepatic clearance (CLH)	Unbound fraction (fub)	Renal elimination (Ke)	Dermal and intestinal absorption (rates & fraction)
A: QSAR only	RIVM QSAR	RIVM QSAR	RIVM QSAR	RIVM QSAR	default
B: htk R package	htk QSAR	htk <i>in vitro</i>	htk <i>in vitro</i>	Glomerular Filtration Rate	default
C: QSAR + <i>in vitro</i>	RIVM QSAR	INRA or literature or htk <i>in vitro</i>	RIVM QSAR	RIVM QSAR	default
D: calibrated	htk QSAR	INRA or literature or htk <i>in vitro</i>	Litterature or default 1	calibrated or default 0	Default 0 (dermal) 1 (oral) or calibrated

A- Parameters determined with QSAR models

Within the QSAR-only parameterization, intestinal absorption parameters were set to default values: the intestinal absorption rate was set to 1 hr^{-1} and the absorbed fraction was set to 1.

Chemical-dependent parameters obtained in the QSAR parameterization are reported in Table 5.

The log- partition coefficients were less correlated than in the htk parameterisation: Pearson's correlation coefficient ranged from -0.46 to 0.9.

Table 5: Chemical-specific parameters obtained with QSAR models

Compound	Species	PCAir	logPC						fub	Ke	CLH	Kp_sc_vs
			Fat	Liver	Poor	Rich	Skin	Skin_sc				
Flutamide	Human	1.96E+09	2.127	0.822	0.632	0.072	0.632	-0.699	0.06	4.29E-03	1.03E+00	0.009
Flutamide	Rat	8.99E+08	1.848	0.394	-0.051	0.869	-0.051	-0.699	0.06	4.68E-05	1.86E-02	0.028

Linuron	Human	1.03E+08	2.116	0.794	0.609	0.093	0.609	-0.699	0.082	5.92E-03	7.49E-01	0.011
Linuron	Rat	4.70E+07	1.805	0.371	-0.056	0.822	-0.056	-0.699	0.082	6.46E-05	1.35E-02	0.034
Dienestrol	Human	8.35E+12	2.155	0.922	0.723	-0.538	0.723	-0.699	0.04	3.87E-05	4.21E+00	0.366
Dienestrol	Rat	4.15E+12	1.947	0.643	0.037	1.384	0.037	-0.699	0.001	1.11E-06	2.88E-02	0.533
Imazalil	Human	4.96E+08	2.144	0.874	0.680	-0.018	0.680	-0.699	0.024	1.69E-03	6.16E-02	0.003
Imazalil	Rat	2.36E+08	1.938	0.458	-0.027	1.000	-0.027	-0.699	0.024	1.85E-05	1.11E-03	0.008
Thiacloprid	Human	1.93E+09	1.927	0.507	0.362	0.124	0.362	-0.699	0.399	2.87E-02	3.60E-01	0.002
Thiacloprid	Rat	8.44E+08	1.446	0.241	-0.102	0.550	-0.102	-0.699	0.399	3.14E-04	6.49E-03	0.007
Clothianidin	Human	4.83E+14	0.481	-0.201	-0.092	-0.066	-0.092	0.551	0.98	1.85E-01	4.96E-01	3E-05
Clothianidin	Rat	2.10E+14	0.041	-0.041	-0.201	-0.032	-0.201	0.551	0.98	2.02E-03	8.94E-03	1E-04
Cyproconazole	Human	7.68E+08	2.081	0.720	0.543	0.124	0.543	-0.699	0.152	1.09E-02	1.50E-02	0.003
Cyproconazole	Rat	3.43E+08	1.703	0.326	-0.071	0.728	-0.071	-0.699	0.152	1.19E-04	2.71E-04	0.01
Triadimefon	Human	6.40E+09	2.058	0.679	0.508	0.130	0.508	-0.699	0.194	1.40E-02	1.27E-02	0.003
Triadimefon	Rat	2.84E+09	1.651	0.307	-0.081	0.688	-0.081	-0.699	0.194	1.53E-04	2.29E-04	0.008
VPA	Human	1.47E+05	0.497	-0.194	-0.092	-0.066	-0.092	-0.699	0.979	1.70E-01	1.30E-02	0.012
VPA	Rat	6.53E+04	0.057	-0.036	-0.201	-0.027	-0.201	-0.699	0.979	1.86E-03	2.35E-04	0.035

B- Parameters extracted from R package htk

Many parameters in the htk parameterization were default values for all compounds. The absorbed fraction was set to 100%, the intestinal absorption rate was set to 1 hr^{-1} , and the dermal absorption rate was set to 0, except for Imazalil where the in vivo data from the literature included a dermal exposure: in that case a default value of $0.01 \text{ dm}\cdot\text{hr}^{-1}$ based on the range of values used over all compounds in the QSAR parameterization. Elimination clearance (K_e) was based on the Glomerular Filtration Rate (GFR) used in htk, equal to $0.3099 \text{ L}\cdot\text{hr}^{-1}\cdot\text{kg BW}^{-3/4}$ in humans and $0.222 \text{ L}\cdot\text{hr}^{-1}\cdot\text{kg BW}^{-3/4}$ in rats, assuming 70 kg humans and 250 g rats.

Chemical-dependent parameters obtained with htk are reported in Table 6.

Metabolism was assumed to be hepatic and to follow first order rather than Michaelis Menten kinetics. Human values of hepatic clearance available in htk were based on screening in vitro tests at $1 \mu\text{M}$ reported in [12] (Flutamide), [13] (VPA), and [14] (all other compounds except dienestrol). Rat values of clearance were based on in vitro tests on rat cells for Imazalil, Cyproconazole, and Triadimefon [15]. For other compounds, intrinsic clearance from human hepatocytes were used.

Unbound fractions in human plasma were based on the screening in vitro tests reported in [12] (Flutamide), by TNO (VPA), and in [14] (other compounds). Unbound fractions in rat plasma were based on in vitro tests on rat plasma for Imazalil, Cyproconazole, and Triadimefon [15], VPA [16,17], For other compounds, the values determined in humans were used.

Tissue: plasma unbound partition coefficients were estimated with htk which uses the method from Schmitt [16,17]. Fat, liver and skin partition coefficients were predicted using the QSAR model by Schmitt. Richly and poorly perfused partition coefficients were set to the values for kidney and muscle respectively. Tissue: blood partition coefficients were then obtained using the blood to plasma ratio and unbound fraction. Dienestrol partition coefficients were all set to 1. The log-partition coefficients are highly correlated (Pearson's correlation coefficient ranged from 0.634 to 0.998).

Table 6: Chemical-specific parameters used for rats and humans, obtained with the htk package.

Compound	Species	ratio blood to plasma	logPC						fub	CLH
			Fat	Liver	Skin	Poor	Rich	Skin_sc		
Flutamide	Human	1.20	4.02	1.58	1.99	-0.0755	1.27	1.99	0.0376	531
Flutamide	Rat	1.17	4.04	1.55	2	-0.0934	1.25	2	0.0376	2.70
Linuron	Human	1.93	4.27	1.85	2.24	0.189	1.55	2.24	0.11	545
Linuron	Rat	1.90	4.29	1.82	2.25	0.165	1.51	2.25	0.11	2.77
Dienestrol	Human	1.00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Dienestrol	Rat	1.00	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Imazalil	Human	2.18	3.94	2.04	2.11	0.672	1.8	2.11	0.03	0
Imazalil	Rat	3.21	4.06	2.11	2.21	0.738	1.86	2.21	0.05	4.85
Thiacloprid	Human	1.23	3.69	1.49	1.73	-0.0331	1.21	1.73	0.29	34.8
Thiacloprid	Rat	1.21	3.71	1.46	1.74	-0.0499	1.18	1.74	0.29	0.177
Clothianidin	Human	0.745	0.93	-0.08	-0.118	-0.435	-0.133	-0.118	0.51	132
Clothianidin	Rat	0.73	0.947	-0.0826	-0.107	-0.422	-0.132	-0.107	0.51	0.670
Cyproconazole	Human	1.24	3.91	1.57	1.9	-0.0515	1.28	1.9	0.11	22.9
Cyproconazole	Rat	1.28	3.97	1.58	1.95	-0.0356	1.28	1.95	0.12	0.175
Triadimefon	Human	7.24	4.72	2.14	2.65	0.462	1.83	2.65	0.11	369
Triadimefon	Rat	0.842	3.79	1.19	1.73	-0.435	0.882	1.73	0.005	1.47
VPA	Human	0.66	0.0168	-0.476	-0.667	-1.37	-0.513	-0.667	0.366	2.15E-05
VPA	Rat	0.600	-0.354	-0.794	-0.884	-1.63	-0.804	-0.884	0.22	1.09E-07

C- Parameters determined with QSAR models and in vitro clearance measurements

Parameterisation C was based on parameterization A (QSAR only) but included hepatic clearance values obtained with *in vitro* clearance measurements.

In vitro measurements of metabolism in primary cultures of human and rat hepatocytes were obtained for linuron, dienestrol, and imazalil in the framework of the Euromix project to obtain parameters for metabolic rate constants (V_{max} , K_m , $CL_{intrinsic}$) for six pesticides: dienestrol, imazalil, linuron, cyproconazole, thiacloprid and clothianidin. Of these molecules, only imazalil, linuron and cyproconazole were available in radiolabelled form. Different analytical methods had to be developed for all these compounds: HPLC with radiochemical detection or DAD detection.

Primary culture of human and animal hepatocytes:

Fresh human or cryopreserved human hepatocytes (laboratory cells bank) were used. For fresh human hepatocytes, the tissue liver was obtained from the Digestive Unit, Archet 2 Hospital, University Hospital of Nice, France. With informed consent of the tissue donor, and following the ethical guidelines, pieces of livers were collected from patient undergoing partial hepatectomy. The studies by Vondran et al. [18] and Hewes et al. [19] report no influence of previous chemotherapy on the isolation outcome or subsequent hepatocytes function. The length of time between chemotherapy and surgery may have allowed functional hepatocyte recovery. Rat and animal hepatocytes were used as after cryopreservation (laboratory cells bank). Cryopreserved hepatocytes were used as previously described in de Sousa et al. [20]. Depending the compound cells were seeded in 48 or 24 multiwell plates in 200 or 500 μ L of culture medium.

Design of experiments

Preliminary experiments have been conducted to determine the concentrations and incubation times that allow the calculation of unchanged product elimination kinetic constants as well as Michaelian constants. Stock solutions and successive dilutions of compounds were prepared in DMSO as a 400 times concentrated solution and then diluted in William's E medium containing no FCS and no phenol red but supplemented with HSA (0.25% DMSO final concentration). Prior to the first experiments, compounds stability in the incubation medium was tested, as well as the nonspecific binding on culture plate. At various intervals times which depend on preliminary experiments, reactions were stopped by addition of 200 μ L (or 500 μ L) of cold acetonitrile. Cells were scraped and stored at -20 °C until analysis. Prior to HPLC analyses the medium/ACN containing cells were submitted to centrifugation to remove proteins. Three to four independent freshly prepared or cryopreserved human and three rat cryopreserved hepatocytes were used for the metabolic study. Radiochemical HPLC methods were developed for imazalil, linuron and cyproconazole ; HPLC DAD method was developed for dienestrol, thiacloprid and clothianidin.

To quantify the number of hepatocytes, 2 to 3 blank wells were fixed with iced MeOH and after coloration by the fluorescent dye HOESCHST 33342, the adherent cells were counted by using an Arrayscan XTI.

Sample and data analysis

The whole hepatocyte extracts from incubations of compounds were analyzed by HPLC with radiochemical detection (Linuron, imazalil, cyproconazole), or DAD detection (dienestrol, thiaclopride, clothianidin) after centrifugation. Unchanged chemicals were quantified.

Data are expressed as mean \pm S.D of at least three independent hepatocyte's experimentations. The data obtained were analyzed based on Michaelis Menten kinetics, substrate velocity curve was calculated using statistical software (Statistica V12.0, Stasoft, France) and used to determine K_m and V_{max} values using nonlinear regression analysis fitting as described in [21]. For dienestrol only intrinsic clearance was determined by fitting $C(t) = C(0) \times e^{-kt}$. Data are expressed as mean \pm S.D.

Results on the *in vitro* metabolism experiments

The results are summarized in Table 11.

- Dienestrol (not radiolabelled)

Two concentrations, 10 and 20 μM were tested. Experiments were performed in four different human hepatocytes preparations (higher variability) and three for rats. The mean number of cells for rat was 15.10^3 and 20.10^3 for human. For both cells, 7 times of exposure was tested. The percentage of the unchanged dienestrol versus time was fitted as $C(t) = C(0) \times e^{-kt}$ (Figure 2). The value of k is expressed as ± 0.95 confidence interval which is used to calculate the *in vitro* intrinsic clearance.

Figure 2 : Percent of unchanged dienestrol (mean \pm -SD) is fitted in order to determine k (elimination rate constant)

Table 7 : Calculated *in vitro* intrinsic clearance for rat and human hepatocytes.

<p>Elimination Constant (10μM) = 0.00608 Elimination constant (20μM) = 0.00683 In Vitro Half life (t1/2) (min) (10μM) = 113.98 In Vitro Half life (t1/2) (min) (20μM) = 101.47 In Vitro Intrinsic clearance 10μM = 20.26 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}/10^6$ cells \pm 1.14 In Vitro Intrinsic clearance 20μM = 25.04 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}/10^6$ cells \pm 0.86</p>	<p>Elimination Constant (10μM) = 0.00565 Elimination constant (20μM) = 0.00505 In Vitro Half life (t1/2) (min) (10μM) = 122.65 In Vitro Half life (t1/2) (min) (20μM) = 137.27 In Vitro Intrinsic clearance 10μM = 14.13 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}/10^6$ cells \pm 0.6 In Vitro Intrinsic clearance 20μM = 12.63 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}/10^6$ cells \pm 0.625</p>
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Imazalil : (^{14}C radiolabelled compound available)

6 concentrations (0.5 to 100 μ M) were used for incubation times ranging from 30 minutes to 24 hours (Figure 3 and Figure 4). The incubation volume was 250 μ L in 48-well plates for a range of hepatocytes from 75,000 for rats to 100,000 for humans. The appearance of (total) metabolites was modelled to determine the initial velocity at each concentration. These values were then used to determine K_m and V_m as described [21].

Figure 3: Rat hepatocytes ; A, Reaction progress curves of total metabolites apparition at 5 different concentration versus time. B, a Michaelis-Menten plot of imazalil metabolites initial velocity versus substrate (imazalil) concentration

Figure 4: Human hepatocytes ; A, Reaction progress curves of total metabolites apparition at 5 different concentrations versus time. B, a Michaelis-Menten plot of imazalil metabolites initial velocity versus substrate (imazalil) concentration

Table 8: Calculated V_m and K_m for rat and human hepatocytes

	Rat		Human	
	Estimate	Standard error	Estimate	Standard error
V_m (nmol/min/number cells)	0.00397 (75000 cells)	0.000230	0.00396(10 ⁵ cells)	0.000372
K_m (μ M)	4.295	0.0724	1.959	0.540

Linuron: (¹⁴C radiolabelled compound available)

6 concentrations (1 to 50 μ M) were used for incubation times ranging from 30 minutes to 24 hours (Figure 5 and Figure 6). The incubation volume was 250 μ L in 48-well plates for a range of hepatocytes from 75,000 for rats to 100,000 for humans. The appearance of (total) metabolites was modelled to determine the initial velocity at each concentration. These values were then used to

determine K_m and V_m as described [21].

Figure 5: Rat hepatocytes ; A, Reaction progress curves of total metabolites apparition at 5 different concentration versus time. B, a Michaelis-Menten plot of linuron metabolites initial velocity versus substrate (imazalil) concentration

Figure 6: Human hepatocytes ; A, Reaction progress curves of total metabolites apparition at 5 different concentration versus time. B, a Michaelis-Menten plot of linuron metabolites initial velocity versus substrate (imazalil) concentration

Table 9: Calculated V_m and K_m for rat and human hepatocytes

	Rat		Human	
	Estimate	Standard error	Estimate	Standard error
V_m (nmol/min/number cells)	0.0135 (75000 cells)	0.00130	0.0302 (100000 cells)	0.00180
K_m (μ M)	9.985	1.609	6.629	0.759

Unbound fractions in hepatocyte incubations were estimated as described in [22] (Table 10).

Table 10 : Unbound fractions in hepatocyte incubations

	Rat (75000 cells for 250 μ L)	Human (100000 cells for 250 μ L)
<i>Imazalil</i>	0.78	0.72
<i>Linuron</i>	0.898	0.87

Conclusions on in vitro measurements of metabolism

As part of the work carried out by the INRA team for WP4, we tested the metabolism of six molecules (instead of the three initially planned) on human and rat hepatocytes. The metabolism rates of imazalil, dienestrol and linuron, allowed the calculation of kinetic constants. The clearance values obtained are within a factor 2 of the values reported in htk for linuron. For imazalil in rats, the new value is 4-fold smaller. However, for dienestrol in both human and rats, and for imazalil in humans, no htk value was available for comparison. Using a clearance value rather than Michaelis Menten kinetics appears to be satisfactory as linuron and imazalil, hepatic concentrations predicted in the various exposure scenarios were smaller than the value of K_m .

For the three other molecules tested (cyproconazole, thiacloprid, and clothianidin), no kinetic constants could be determined. The different tests on these three compounds (concentration, incubation time of the species tested: human, rat, monkey and dog) always showed a very low turn over for very long exposure times. Furthermore, these molecules are already described in the literature as being poorly metabolized in animal species with very high liver levels of unchanged product. Analytical techniques may therefore not be sufficiently sensitive and, most importantly, the various metabolites that would have allowed to refine the analytical methods could not be obtained.

In vitro data from the literature

Metabolism of flutamide was quantified in several publications (see below). For the remaining five molecules (thiacloprid, clothianidin, cyproconazole, triadimefon and VPA), *in vitro* clearances were obtained with the htk package as in parameterization B, but the unbound fractions determined by QSAR models were used.

In vitro metabolism of flutamide was quantified by [23–26] in either rat cells, or human cells, or both. Three metabolic pathways of flutamide were identified, hydroxylation and hydrolysis to Flu-1 and Flu-6. The relative contributions of each pathway depend on the concentration in the liver. The relative contributions are represented in Figure 7, assuming $P_{CLiver}=1$ and $f_{ub}=0.05$ (intermediate values of QSAR and htk parameterisations). Hydrolysis to Flu-6 is negligible compared to the other two pathways and realistic internal concentrations. Hydrolysis to Flu-1 also appears to be negligible at hepatic concentrations smaller than $10\mu M$. The concentrations observed in liver in humans and rats in the data collected were smaller than $1\mu M$, and therefore the metabolism rate could be approximated by the clearance estimated as hydroxylation V_{max} divided by K_m . However, the predictions using QSAR and *in vitro* parameters reached predicted concentrations around $10\mu M$ in rats (equivalent to 6.74 with $P_{CLiver}=1.48$). In this range of concentrations, although hydroxylation is still the main pathway, metabolism is slightly overestimated when using the clearance value.

Extrapolation of flutamide clearances per unit of weight was carried out from rat to human using the same factor 0.703 as used in htk. The unbound fraction in liver used was the one provided for humans in htk. In the case of flutamide, linuron, and imazalil, hepatic concentrations predicted in the various exposure scenarios were smaller than the K_m in Michaelis Menten kinetics.

Table 11: *In vitro* metabolism parameters for flutamide, linuron, dienestrol, and imazalil

Compound	Species		Vmax (pmol/min)	Km (μM)	Clint ($\mu\text{L}/\text{min}/10^6$ cells)	Fraction unbound in liver	Clearance (L/h)
Flutamide	human	Flu to 2-Flu-OH	extrapolated			0.665 (httk)	405
		Flu to Flu-1 [23,24]	1900 \pm 100 /mg protein	1100			
		Flu to Flu-6 [25]	1.78 /mg protein	86			
	rat	Flu to 2-Flu-OH [26]	282 \pm 33 /mg protein	4.03 \pm 0.54		0.665 (httk human)	3.63
		Flu to Flu-1 [23,24]	2900 \pm 300 /mg protein	1000			
		Flu to Flu-6	extrapolated				
Linuron	human		30.2 \pm 1.80 /10 ⁵ cells	6.63 \pm 0.760		0.87	580
	rat		13.5 \pm 1.29 /75000 cells	9.99 \pm 1.61		0.90	1.39
Dienestrol	human				14.1 \pm 0.60		157 \pm 6.65
	rat				20.3 \pm 1.14		1.40 \pm 0.079
Imazalil	human		3.95 \pm 0.372 /10 ⁵ cells	1.96 \pm 0.539		0.72	310
	rat		3.97 \pm 0.230 /75000 cells	4.30 \pm 0.724		0.78	1.09

Figure 7: Contribution of the three metabolic pathways of flutamide in humans (A) and in rats (B) as a function of the flutamide concentration in liver divided by the blood:liver partition coefficient, which represents the concentration that is available in the liver for metabolism, or venous blood in the liver.

A- Parameters calibrated using *in vivo* data

The fourth parameterization used makes use of the work described in deliverable D4.1. In the framework of WP4, some PBPK model parameters were calibrated to fit *in vivo* data. The PBPK models used were either the one used by URV and adapted to each case (flutamide, linuron, dienestrol, thiacloprid, clothianidin and triadimefon/ triadimenol), or the generic model (imazalil, cyproconazole, valproic acid).

PBPK model parameters for flutamide, linuron, dienestrol, thiacloprid, clothianidin, and triadimefon

The baseline model was for rat and we extrapolated this to the human by adapting the tissue volumes, blood flows through the tissues and the V_{max} per unit microsomal protein, and the fraction of microsomal protein per organ on the basis of experimental data. Partition coefficients were considered the same for rat and human.

Prostate volume and blood flow were estimated from the reported literature data, for humans [27,28] and for rats [29]. As per requirement of PBPK, these data were converted into fraction of body weight and fraction of cardiac blood flow, respectively.

The chemical-specific parameters for flutamide, linuron, dienestrol, thiacloprid, clothianidin, and triadimefon determined in the modified PBPK model were then extracted and used in the generic PBPK as summarized in Table 12. Details on the chemical-specific parameter values and distributions in the modified PBPK model are provided in Appendix 1. The parameters that were adjusted to fit the data were the renal excretion rate (flutamide, clothianidin).

For flutamide, chemical rate constants and metabolic parameters are provided in Table 1 of Appendix 1. The oral absorption process in humans for flutamide was described through a first order absorption rate constant of 0.62 h^{-1} [30] in both single and multiple oral dose simulations.

We interpreted detailed rat *in vivo* data reported in [31] through a method introduced by [32] and effectively adapted by others [33], This method uses the trapezoidal rule to derive tissue partition coefficients ($K_{i:p}$) from the AUC (area under the curve) observed in *in vivo* animal kinetic profile data of plasma and tissues

$$K_{i:p} = \frac{AUC_{\text{tissue}(0-48)}}{AUC_{\text{plasma}(0-48)}} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

Where, $AUC_{\text{tissue}(0-48)}$ represents the area under the curve for the tissue concentration-time curves from 0 to 48 h.

The average binding percentage of flutamide with plasma protein was reported for rats and human as 60.6 and 91.9 %, respectively [34]. The reported mean value of 95% for Flu-OH (flutamide hydroxide) for human was used to derive the fraction unbound for Flu-OH, which has also been previously used by [35] for the development of a semi physiologically-based pharmacokinetic model. We assumed that intracellularly the same fraction of flutamide is bound to intracellular proteins.

Flutamide metabolism is described as a Michaelis-Menten saturable process (Eq.2) with parameters V_{max} (maximum velocity of metabolic reaction) and K_m (1/affinity, i.e. concentration at which reaction occurs at half maximal rate). The reported *in vitro* V_{max} values for the tissue microsomal fraction were scaled to *in vivo* values using the IVIVE approach [36], whereas K_m values were kept the same as the *in vitro* value.

$$V_{A_{\text{mets}}} = \frac{V_{\text{max}} * C_t * f_u}{K_m + C_t * f_u} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

Where, C_t is the corresponding concentration in tissue and f_u is the fraction unbound.

$v_{A_{\text{mets}}}$ is the rate of production of metabolites.

The *in vitro-in vivo* extrapolation (IVIVE) approach utilizes physiological specific parameters such as tissue specific microsomal protein content, specific tissue volume and body weight described in Eq. (3) [37,38]. Eq. (3) involves the extrapolation of the specific activity from *in vitro* measured to *in vivo* whole body, used for the both rat and human using species specific physiological data such as microsomal protein content of tissue, tissue volume and body weight

$$V_{\text{max}}_{\text{in vivo}} = (V_{\text{max}}_{\text{in vitro}} * \text{MSPPGT} * V_{\text{tissue}}) / \text{BW}^{.75} \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

Where, MSPPGT is the microsomal protein per gram tissue; V_{tissue} is the volume of tissue; BW is the body weight and its power to $^{.75}$ is to normalize the scaled Vmax for different human body weights.

The *in-vitro* data such as Vmax and Km for flutamide metabolism in rats were taken from [39]. This study reported on flutamide metabolism in different tissue cell lines. The *in vitro* measured specific activity (Vmax) for liver, lung and kidney were scaled to whole body in order to obtain the *in vivo* specific intrinsic clearance. For the development of the human PBPK model, the biochemical parameters such as Vmax and Km describing metabolism of flutamide into 3 different metabolites (Figure 8) were taken from *in-vitro* hepatic cell line studies [24–26]. However, only flutamide hydroxide, which is the major metabolite, was distributed to plasma from the liver site using the same partition coefficient to that of the parent compound. Due to lack of specific data on the generation of different metabolites, no metabolites were included in the current rat PBPK model. However, clearance of flutamide is considered in that model, including its metabolism in rat lung, rat liver and rat kidney as reported by [39] in *in vitro* cell line studies. Elimination rate constants for both flutamide and flutamide hydroxide were visually optimized to fit the plasma data of human studies carried out by Radwanski et al. [40]. The flutamide elimination rate constant was optimized in order to match the observed data knowing the fact that there are some unknown flutamide catabolism pathways.

Figure 8: Schema for human flutamide metabolism; Liver CYP1A2 metabolizes flutamide into flutamide hydroxide, main metabolite. Deacetylation of flutamide by carboxylesterase generates FlU-1. Reduction of aromatic nitro group into amino group by cytochrome reductase results in conversion of Flutamide to FLU-6.

Generic PBPK model parameters for imazalil, cyproconazole and valproic acid

For most parameters, *a priori* information from the literature, QSAR models or *in vitro* experiments (even if imprecise) were used. The parameters that were adjusted so that the model predictions matched the data were hepatic clearance (valproic acid, imazalil in humans), skin diffusion coefficient (imazalil), fraction absorbed by gut, oral absorption rate, renal excretion rate, unbound fraction in blood (imazalil in humans). No adjustments were made for cyproconazole.

Table 12: Chemical-specific parameters used for rats and humans, used in the parameterisation with calibration.

Compound	Species	ratio blood to plasma	logPCFat	logPCLiver	logPCSkin	logPCPoor	logPCRich	logPCSkin_sc
Flutamide	Human	1.20	0.444	0.746	0.746	0.746	0.420	0.746
Flutamide	Rat	1.17	0.444	0.746	0.746	0.746	0.420	0.746
Linuron	Human	1.93	1.91	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.43	0.65
Linuron	Rat	1.90	1.91	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.43	0.65
Dienestrol	Human	1.00	2.27	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.79	1.00
Dienestrol	Rat	1.00	2.27	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.79	1.00
Imazalil	Human	2.18	3.6	0.7	-0.44	-0.44	0.7	-4.04
Imazalil	Rat	3.21	3.6	0.7	-0.44	-0.44	0.7	-4.04
Thiacloprid	Human	1.23	0.0899	0.415	0.415	0.415	0.223	0.415
Thiacloprid	Rat	1.21	0.0899	0.415	0.415	0.415	0.223	0.415

Clothianidin	Human	0.745	-0.409	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.255	0.250
Clothianidin	Rat	0.73	-0.409	0.250	0.250	0.250	0.255	0.250
Cyproconazole	Human	1.24	1.96	-0.92	-1.61	-1.61	-0.92	-3.57
Cyproconazole	Rat	1.28	1.96	-0.92	-1.61	-1.61	-0.92	-3.57
Triadimefon	Human	7.24	2.06	1.09	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.65
Triadimefon	Rat	0.842	2.06	1.09	0.65	0.65	0.65	0.65
VPA	Human	0.66	-1.83	-3.1	-3.22	-3.22	-2.85	-1.39
VPA	Rat	0.600	-1.83	-3.1	-3.22	-3.22	-2.85	-1.39

Table 12 (continued): Chemical-specific parameters used for rats and humans, used in the parameterisation with calibration.

Compound	Species	Frac	kGut	Ke	Kp_sc_vs	fub	CLH
Flutamide	Human	0.5	0.64	1.25	0	0.09	4469
Flutamide	Rat	0.5	0.5	0.07	0	0.4	26.5
Linuron	Human	1	1	7.62	0	1	57.5
Linuron	Rat	1	1	0.201	0	1	0.0795
Dienestrol	Human	1	1	9.48	0	0.6	283
Dienestrol	Rat	1	1	0.25	0	0.6	3.00
Imazalil	Human	0.8	10	17	1.00E-05	0.05	70
Imazalil	Rat	0.8	1	0.09	2.00E-05	0.015	6
Thiacloprid	Human	1	1	2.27	0	1	0
Thiacloprid	Rat	1	1	0.06	0	1	0
Clothianidin	Human	1	1	2.27	0	1	0
Clothianidin	Rat	1	1	0.06	0	1	0
Cyproconazole	Human	0.996	1	0	0.1	0.07	0
Cyproconazole	Rat	0.996	1	0	0.1	0.11	0.21
Triadimefon	Human	1	1	9.21	0	1	0
Triadimefon	Rat	1	1	0.243	0	1	0
VPA	Human	0.996	2.88	0	0.1	0.14	8.8
VPA	Rat	0.996	2.88	0	0.1	0.14	0.4

Integrating uncertainty and variability

Modelling of uncertainty and variability of PBPK model parameters

It is important for risk assessment to dissociate uncertainty in model parameter values (for example when they have been obtained from QSARs) and variability of those parameters in the population (for example, we do not have all the same mass of fat tissue). Uncertainty can be eventually reduced by the collection of additional data, more refined models, *etc.* Variability cannot be reduced, but just better estimated by the observation of more individuals. When making predictions about a future individual in a hypothetical exposure scenario, uncertainty and variability compound and it may not be necessary to reduce uncertainty to a minimum if variability is very large. Several approaches can be taken to estimate the impact of uncertainty and variability on predicted pharmacokinetics, but they mostly rely on Monte Carlo simulations to be performed [5]. Depending on the compound and the exposure scenario, the output of a PBPK model may be or less sensitive to the various physiological or compound-specific parameters. For example, in the case of chronic exposure to a lipophilic compound, the variability of the fat compartment volume may strongly impact the variability in whole body levels. In our case, predictive modeling with Monte-Carlo simulations is in order, since it is not foreseen that we will have the capabilities and data to do inferential modeling (*i.e.*, population pharmacokinetic modeling). Predictive Monte Carlo modeling for simulating uncertainty and variability is best understood in a hierarchical framework. First, we are typically uncertain about the population mean values (*e.g.*, the average metabolic clearance of a given molecule), and next we suspect inter-individual variability around those average values. Two-stage Monte Carlo sampling therefore proceeds by first sampling randomly, out of a specified distribution representing uncertainty, a mean value, and then, around that mean value, with a given population variability, a second random variate, taken as the individual value when simulating the model. Indeed, this should be done for all model parameters before a given run. In INERIS and DLO experience and with the *GNU MCSim* software, one Monte Carlo simulation takes of the order of 10 milli-seconds. The simulation time does not depend appreciably on the number of parameters sampled, but rather on the length of the simulation scenario and the density of separate exposure events it contains. More simulations give more precise estimations of the target distribution tails, but the precision obtained may be illusory, since it depends on the precision of the prior parameter mean and variability, which we can only roughly estimate.

As to the actual values assigned to coefficients of variation for uncertainty and variability, we can differentiate between expert-based estimates and data-based estimates.

Expert-based uncertainty and variability estimates

Expert-based judgement has been exercised in the scientific literature over the past 20 years (*e.g.* [15-19]), and has commonly assumed, for humans, the values given in Table 13. The coefficients of variation (CV) used for uncertainty in physiological parameters (when scaled to body mass or similarly) are usually set to 10, 20 or 30%. The higher value is used for ventilation rate and fat mass. The CVs for variability are usually of 10 or 20%. For partition coefficients obtained from *in silico* methods, uncertainty is considered to be of the order of a factor 3. The variability of partition coefficients usually reflects the variability in blood lipids and a CV of 30% is used. Metabolic and transport processes, driven by enzymes, have also a high uncertainty, when obtained by *in vitro* methods (by a factor 3). Their variability is also high, because of polymorphisms, and CVs of 50% (for

affinity or Michaelis-Menten constants) or a factor 2 (for Vmax or clearance values) are used. These can be proposed as default estimates and should be refined for parameters measured more accurately (for example *in vivo*). For animals, the estimates are about the same, except that variability between inbred animals would not be expected to be higher than 50% for metabolism and transport processes. Table 13 suggests a priori estimates of uncertainty and variability for physiological parameters, chemical-specific partition coefficients and metabolism and transport rates.

Table 13: A priori (expert-based) estimates of uncertainty and variability for PBPK model parameters.

Parameter type	Uncertainty (fold-change)	Variability (fold-change)
Physiological parameters	1.1, 1.2, 1.3	1.1, 1.2
Partition coefficients	3	1.3
Metabolism and transport	3	1.5, 2

Actual simulations require the definition of a sampling distribution. Normal distributions (truncated to be above zero when needed) and log-normal distributions are commonly used. Their variance parameters should be set to match the prescribed CV or fold-change. The choice of distributions does not matter too much for low CVs (10, 20%), but has an impact for higher CVs. Authors have also imposed bounds (*e.g.*, two or three standard deviations around the mean) to limit the occurrence of extreme values (but see our remark about tail precision above).

Application of uncertainty modelling

When the PBPK model was used to predict internal concentration following theoretical or experimental exposure scenarios, 10,000 Monte Carlo simulations were performed in each exposure scenario, by simulating uncertainty on partition coefficients, oral absorption rate, fraction absorbed, hepatic clearance, elimination rate and unbound fraction in plasma.

In this report, physiological parameters were set to the values reported in Table 1 and Table 2. No variabilities of physiological or chemical-specific parameters was modelled. Uncertainty on chemical-specific parameters was modelled using log-normal and truncated log-normal distributions where the standard deviation of the log-transformed parameters was set to log(3), which is equivalent to a 3 fold deviation on the parameter. In the present report, truncated log-normal distributions were used for the unbound fraction [0;1] and the orally absorbed fraction [0;1] if they were smaller than 0.5. Otherwise, a truncated normal distribution was used. In MCRA on the other hand, the logistic normal distribution is used. As reported in D4.2, to account for the fact that partition coefficients for a given chemical (in particular when computed with QSAR methods) are typically strongly correlated, they are made proportional to the fat over blood partition coefficient:

$$PC_{fat} = \exp(\log PC_{fat}) \quad (1)$$

$$PC_i = PC_{fat} \times \exp(\log A_i) \quad (2)$$

with $\log A_i$ the log of PC_i over PC_{fat} ratio, and i belonging to set $\{liv, r, p, s, sc\}$ (for liver, richly perfused, poorly perfused, viable skin, and stratum corneum, respectively). Therefore, in the MonteCarlo simulations, PCfat and the scaling factors A_i are lognormally distributed and proportional to each other. Examples of distributions of chemical-specific parameters are shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Distribution of a selection of chemical-specific parameters for flutamide in humans with the httk parameterisation. Estimates for these parameters were the following: $\log_PC_{fat}=4.02$, $CLH=531L/h$, $fub=0.376$, $Frac=1$, $kGut=11/h$, $Ke=7.5L/h$

Model application and verification

The PBPK model was applied to 9 substances belonging to 3 families with the final aim of performing cumulative risk assessment. Before performing *in vitro* – *in vivo* extrapolation using the PBTK model, the quality of prediction of the PBTK model was checked for each compound based on *in vivo* data on kinetics. The COSMOS model was therefore used with three different parameterizations to predict internal concentrations according to the exposure scenarios used in the *in vivo* studies available from the literature.

The Cosmos implementation in MCRA can be run with any parameter set, so both human and animal models can be specified. However, currently only the use of the human model is implemented in MCRA. At the exposure side, it is the human model that is needed to translate external human exposure to internal exposure. At the hazard side, different approaches can be used. The currently implemented approach is to translate first points of departure from animal studies to a human equivalent using an interspecies factor. After this, it is again the human kinetic model that is used to translate back and forth between external and internal doses. An alternative approach would be to replace the kinetic part of the interspecies factor by the use of both the animal and the human kinetic model.

Human *in vivo* data on internal kinetics was only available for pharmaceutical chemicals, in blood (or plasma) or in urine. The PBPK model for other compounds was therefore checked using the rat PBPK model, under the assumption that, since the chemical-specific data was either identical or at least obtained with a similar methodology for rats and humans, the quality of prediction would be similar if the human PBPK model were to be checked with human data.

In vivo data on kinetics was collected from the literature in humans and rats (Table 14). Data on flutamide and valproic acid were collected in both species. For imazalil, as data was only found in humans, only the human parameterization of the PBPK model was checked. Conversely, for thiacloprid, clothianidin, cyproconazole, and triadimefon, data was only available in rat, and so only the rat parameterization was checked. No data was found on *in vivo* kinetics of dienestrol or linuron. The data collected in rats on thiacloprid, clothianidin, and cyproconazole was expressed as equivalents of administered dose, as it was obtained using autoradiography.

Table 14: Available *in vivo* data on kinetics

Compound	Organism	Organ / Tissue	Dose	Description of data	Source
Flutamide	human	plasma	250, 500 mg oral	C _{max} , AUC	[41]Schulz
		plasma	250 mg/day, oral once then 3 times a day 8 days	0-72 hr after dose	[40]Radwanski [42]Anjum
	rat	plasma	15 mg/kg, oral	0-4 hrs	[43]Zuo
Dienestrol				--	
Linuron				--	
Imazalil	human	urine	0.05 mg/kg, dermal, 8 hours 0.025 mg/kg, oral	0-120 hrs	unpublished data (Faniband et al.)
Thiacloprid	rat	organs	1, 5, 100 mg/kg oral	Radioactivity up to 72 hrs	[44]FAO report (unpublished data)
		plasma	1 mg/kg IV		
		excreta	1 mg/kg/day 14days oral		
Clothianidin	rat	organs, plasma, excreta	2.5, 5, 250 mg/kg oral 25 mg/kg/day 14days oral	Radioactivity up to 168 hrs	[45]FAO report (unpublished data)
		organs, blood	5, 250 mg/kg oral 5 mg/kg oral	2, 24, 48 hrs 5 min to 48 hrs	[46]Yokota
Cyproconazole	rat	organs, excreta	10 mg/kg, oral + IV 0.5 mg/kg/day 7 days oral 130mg/kg oral	up to 168 hrs	[45]FAO report (unpublished data)
Triadimefon / triadimenol	rat	plasma, liver, kidney, brain, fat	50 mg/kg iv	Also TNL dosed in plasma 5min to 24hrs	[47]Crowell
Valproic acid	human	serum	1000 mg twice oral, 900 mg twice iv, 1000 mg iv	0-110 hr	[48]Nitsche
		plasma, blood	600 mg iv, oral	0-28 hrs	[49]Klotz
		plasma	250 mg, oral	0-36 hr,	[50] Chun
		plasma	15 mg/kg, iv	0-6 hrs	[51]Cloyd
	rat	serum	800 mg, oral (and IV)	0-48 hrs	[52]Perucca
		serum	1000 mg, oral	0-48 hrs	[53]Bialer
		plasma	200, 600 mg oral	total and free VPA, 0-24hrs	[54]Binkerd

Once the model performance with the various parameterisations had been checked against *in vivo* data, the impact of the various parameterisations on critical steps of cumulative risk assessment was evaluated:

- 1- Using continuous exposure scenarios with 1 mg/kg BW/day of each substance, the human to rat internal concentration ratios were calculated. This can be performed in any target organ; here the results in blood are reported.
- 2- Inside each cumulative assessment group, the internal concentrations of each substance were calculated, again simulating continuous exposure scenarios with 1 mg/kg BW/day. The kinetic absorption factors, which relate the internal concentrations at a target organ to the daily exposure per unit of bodyweight were also calculated. These factors allow an easy extrapolation of internal to external dose-response relationships.

Using the PBPK model in risk assessment

Theoretical framework

Toxicological data (dose-response data) may in general be available from measurements in different **systems**, defined by where the dose-effect relation is measured, e.g.:

1. in-vivo human target-organ dose
2. in-vivo human external dose (oral, dermal or inhalation)
3. in-vivo animal target-organ dose
4. in-vivo animal external dose (oral, dermal or inhalation)
5. in-vitro target dose

Doses can be expressed in different units depending on the system, e.g. exposure mass (mg), exposure per unit body weight (mg/kg of body mass) or concentration (mg/L). In-vivo experiments most often report external dose data, and human data are very sparse for chemicals such as pesticides and contaminants. Therefore, we need to model dose-to-dose conversions, e.g.:

1. external (oral, dermal, inhalation) dose to target dose (animal or human PBPK model)
2. animal external dose to the human external dose leading to the same effect level (inter-species external dose model)
3. animal internal dose to human internal dose (inter-species internal dose model)
4. in-vitro dose to animal target-organ dose or external dose (animal QIVIVE model)
5. in-vitro dose to human target-organ dose or external dose (human QIVIVE model)

The conversion from an external dose to an effect in humans or in animals is a straightforward question which relies on the PBPK model, for the external to internal dose conversion, and on dose-response modelling using target organ concentrations (Figure 10). Sometimes, for animals, *in vivo* dose-response relationships can be established.

Figure 10: Dose to dose extrapolation in humans

Conversion from animal external dose to the human external dose leading to the same effect level is only of use under the assumption that the relationship between internal dose and effect is the same in animals and humans. In that case, the animal PBPK model is used to convert the animal external dose to internal dose and the human PBPK model is used to estimate the human external dose by reverse dosimetry (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Case with identical relationship in animals and humans. Circles: unknown quantities; Squares: known quantities. Black arrows: causal relationships (or models); Double lines: equality assumptions; Red arrows: information flow. The shortest path should be taken.

If the relationship between internal dose and effect is not the same in animals and humans, internal dose to effect data in humans is required. This can sometimes be estimated based on *in vitro* experiments with dose-response modelling. The human external dose can then be estimated with the PBPK model using reverse dosimetry.

The Euromix toolbox includes both forward (external dose to internal concentration) and reverse (internal concentration to external dose) dosimetry.

Calibration of *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation in cumulative risk assessment

We consider a cumulative risk assessment of two substances A and B for human health effects, with dose-response (DR) data from an *in-vivo* test system for one or some substances, and DR data from an *in-vitro* test system for these and other substances:

DATA AVAILABILITY	substance set A	substance set B
1. <i>in vitro</i> test system	✓	✓
2. <i>in vivo</i> test system (e.g. rat)	✓	✗
3. (human) target system	✗	✗

Inside the cumulative risk assessment group, cumulated effects are assumed to be dose-additive.

Suitable dose-response models are assumed to have been identified and can be fitted for multiple substances assuming dose-additivity, both for the *in-vitro* and the *in vivo* data.

This example of cumulative risk assessment requires that the measured response in the *in vivo* test system is the same as in humans for equal internal concentrations: DR relationships based on internal dose are the same (but unmeasured). Substance-specific human kinetic models KM are available to translate the external dose into an internal dose ($KM_{hum,i}$, $i \in \{A, B\}$).

The proposed calibration is as follows:

1. **In-vivo study dose-response modelling:** From the *in vivo* dose-response data (only available for set A, DR_{2A}) and the benchmark response for the adverse outcome (BMR) derive, e.g. using PROAST, external hazard doses (e.g. benchmark doses) HD_{2j} , $j \in A$.
2. **Translate animal BMDs to human BMDs:** Apply an interspecies factor to represent a conservative assumption about interspecies differences. Alternatively, just use the animal BMD as if it were a human BMD, and take the inter-species uncertainty into account in the final evaluation of margins of exposure.

Specific factors are suggested for toxicodynamic aspects (TD) of the interspecies modelling (default 1), extrapolation from shorter exposure durations, e.g. subchronic-to-chronic extrapolation (default >1 . See WHO/ICPS (2014), p.41, where some proposals are made, e.g. $P50=2$ and $P95=8$ for a sub-chronic to chronic extrapolation), NOAEL to BMD conversion (See WHO/ICPS (2014), p.39, where for certain types of endpoint AFs are proposed, e.g. $P50=1/3$, $P95=1.6$ for a continuous endpoint in a chronic or sub-chronic study).

Variability between more and less sensitive individuals in the human population and uncertainty about this variability can be modelled as proposed in Appendix A2 of Van der Voet et al. (2009) (or by using an intra-species factor at a lower tier).

1. **Apply human kinetic models:** From HD_{2j} and the human kinetic model KM_{3j} derive the internal hazard doses IHD_j for $j \in A$. Note that the internal doses are assumed to be the same in all three systems. If set A has more than one substance, derive (internal) relative potency factors relative to the chosen index substance $RPF_j = IHD_{index}/IHD_j$, for $j \in A$.
2. **In-vitro study dose-response modelling:** From the *in-vitro* dose-response data (available for all substances in sets A and B) derive (internal) relative potency factors RPF_j , for $j \in \{A, B\}$. Note that these RPFs apply to all three systems at the internal level.
3. Apply these to IHD_{index} to obtain internal benchmark doses IHD_j for $j \in \{A, B\}$.
4. **Reverse dosimetry:** Use the human kinetic models to translate the IHD_j to HD_j for $j \in \{A, B\}$ and derive (external) relative potency factors RPF_j , for $j \in \{A, B\}$.

5. **Relative potency modelling:** For substances in set A there are now two estimates of RPF, from in-vivo and in-vitro. One option is that in-vivo results will take precedence over in-vitro results. In the EuroMix project, set A was restricted to just the index substance, so all RPFs were based on in-vitro.
6. **Cumulative exposure modelling:** Cumulate the target (external) exposures in terms of the index substance: $EXP_{3,cum} = \sum_j (RPF_j \cdot EXP_{3j})$, for $j \in \{A, B\}$.
7. **Risk characterisation:** From $EXP_{3,cum}$ and HD_{index} derive risk characterisations such as a Margin of Exposure (also known as Cumulative Risk Index): $MOE = CRI = HD_{index} / EXP_{3,cum}$ or a Hazard Index $HI = EXP_{3,cum} / HD_{index}$.

These calculations have been inserted in the already existing two-dimensional variability-uncertainty framework of the EuroMix toolbox MCRA: the variables above will be distributions describing uncertainty of scalar quantities (e.g. HD_{2j}), or uncertainty distributions of percentiles of distributions describing variability (e.g. $EXP_{3,cum}$, MOE).

Mapping of time scales between PB-PK models and risk assessment

PBPK models predict concentrations over time in several compartments. To be of use in risk assessment, this output must be summarized so that an external dose may be converted to an internal dose at the target organ.

1. In risk assessment, health effects are schematized as being either acute or chronic, associated with short-term and long-term exposure, respectively. For example, the Acute Reference Dose (ARfD) and the Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI) are common Human Dose (HD) metrics used in practice for acute and chronic risks, respectively.
2. It can be noted that in risk assessment the dietary exposure data have usually no greater resolution than one day, and the preferred model to obtain dietary data is that the sampled days of each person are non-consecutive (although some historical datasets do have series of consecutive days). It is common to associate exposure integrated over 1 day with acute health effects, and exposure integrated over an indeterminate longer period (e.g. the mean exposure over all sampled days) with chronic health effects.
3. In kinetic experiments, dose X and effect Y can have any sort of temporal resolution, and the question arises how to link time series, which seem to be the typical output of kinetic modelling, to the coarser definitions of hazard in risk assessment, as described above.
4. The simplest model for acute risk seems the peak target-organ dose within a day as a result of a single bolus (exposure at a single time point). Here we propose a model which also allows for background exposure from previous days. We will calculate the average over per-day peak target-organ doses in an experiment with one dose per day, and calculated in a period with assumed pseudo steady-state.

5. The simplest model for chronic risk seems the steady-state target-organ dose (integrated over a suitable exposure period with assumed pseudo steady-state) as a result of a fixed or random exposure pattern over time (e.g. on each day draw a random exposure from a distribution).

Rat to human effect level extrapolation

In vivo animal data may be integrated in risk assessment provided the difference in kinetics between animal and human is known and the internal dose-response relationships are the same in animal and human. A simple way is to use a factor analogous to the Relative Potency Factor (RPF) between chemicals, but which describes the ratio of human and animal benchmark doses, the interspecies relative potency factor.

When considering only the administered dose, the interspecies RPFs obtained *in vivo* for different substances will reflect both differences in toxicokinetics between species and differences in internal dose-responses. When two species display differences in bioaccumulation at the target organ, Interspecies RPFs based on administered doses are therefore specific to the exposure scenario investigated: the interspecies RPFs in case of acute and chronic exposure may differ considerably. The interspecies RPFs should therefore be derived based on target organ dose, as given by PBPK modeling, to integrate differences in kinetics between the animal under study and humans.

If the PBPK model is linear, the internal concentration will be proportional to the external doses and internal interspecies RPFs can be calculated by multiplying the external interspecies RPFs by a correction factor equal to the ratio of administered dose over target concentration. In this case, there is no need to run the human and rat PBPK models the rat PBPK model need not be implemented. The only non-linear component in the selected PBPK model is the Michaelis-Menten metabolism.

The PBPK model was applied to 9 substances and verified against *in vivo* data to check whether interspecies RPFs could be used to extrapolate from animal to human without running both animal and human PBPK models. For each compound, daily oral doses of 1mg/kg were simulated in both human and rat models, with the aim to reach steady state.

Software

A data model was made to accommodate the needed inputs (exposures and parameter values) and outputs of the kinetic models, as well as specifications of their possible variability (between persons, or person-days) and uncertainty. The EuroMix platform organises all needed inputs, and the calculated outputs in tables according to the data model, such that the models are available to stakeholders.

RESULTS

Deviations between predicted internal concentrations and in-vivo data

The PBPK model was applied to the nine selected chemicals, using the three set of parameters defined in section Methods and the exposure scenarios defined in the *in vivo* data on kinetics

collected from the literature (Table 14), obtained with oral or intravenous administration. Model predictions were compared to the *in vivo* data reported in Table 14. Model predictions are compared to observations in a selection of exposure scenarios with QSAR and httk parameterisations in Figure 1 to 4 in SI for humans and in Figure 5 to 14 in SI for rats.

Predicted concentrations in blood or plasma, liver, skin, and fat were compared to the data collected from the literature (Figure 12 and Figure 13). With thiacloprid, clothianidin, and cyproconazole in rats, data represented both parent compound and metabolites; concentrations are therefore expected to be underpredicted. For these compounds, graphical comparisons of predictions and observations are provided (Figure 14 and Figure 15) but the deviation factors are not reported. With the httk and the QSAR + *in vitro* parameterization, plasma concentrations were predicted using the predicted arterial blood concentration and the blood to plasma ratio reported in httk (Table 6).

Figure 12: Predicted vs. observed plasmatic concentrations (Flutamide and VPA) or cumulated amounts excreted in urine (Imazalil, μmol) in humans. Black= A) QSAR parameterization, red= B) httk parameterization, green= C) QSAR + *in vitro* parameterization, blue = D) *in vivo* parameterisation.

Figure 13: Predicted vs. observed concentrations in rats for flutamide, triadimefon, and VPA. A) QSAR parameters, B) httk parameters, C) QSAR + *in vitro* parameters, D) *in vivo* parameterisation.

Figure 14: Predicted vs. observed concentrations in rats for thiocloprid administered in 1, 5, and 100mg/kg BW single oral doses, 1mg/kg BW /day repeated oral doses, or 1mg/kg single IV dose.. Grey lines are used to show that the observations represent the parent compound and metabolites and that the parent compound concentrations are actually equal or smaller than the data points reported. A) QSAR parameters, B) htkk parameters, C) QSAR + in vitro parameters, D) in vivo parameterisation.

Figure 15: Predicted vs. observed concentrations in rats for clothianidin administered in 2.5, 5, and 250 mg/kg BW single oral doses and 25 mg/kg BW /day repeated oral doses, and for cyproconazole administered in 10 and 130 mg/kg single oral doses, 10mg/kg BW single IV doses, 0.5mg/kg BW/day repeated oral doses. Grey lines are used to show that the observed concentrations of the parent compound are equal or smaller than the data points reported. A) QSAR parameters, B) htkk parameters, C) QSAR + in vitro parameters D) in vivo parameterisation.

The predictions obtained with the htkk parameterization are generally lower than those obtained with the QSAR estimates possibly due to faster elimination or metabolism. The elimination clearances based on the GFR are indeed larger than those estimated with QSAR models and, apart for dienestrol (for which there are no htkk estimates), imazalil in humans, and VPA (poorly metabolized in vitro), the clearances based on in vitro tests and reported in htkk are larger than those estimated using QSAR models.

Quality of predictions was assessed by computing fold deviations from observations over the limit of quantification. With the human data and the QSAR only or QSAR + in vitro parameterization, 55% of the predictions were within a 10-fold factor. With the htkk parameterization, 85% of the predictions were within a factor 10. With parameterization D where some model parameters were calibrated, 86% of the predictions were within a factor 10. Amongst the *ab initio* parameterisations A, B and C, the median fold deviation is smallest with the htkk parameterization (3-fold).

With the rat data - excluding radioactivity data – and QSAR parameterization, 37% of the predictions were within a 10-fold factor. With the htk parameterization, 36% of the predictions were within a 10-fold factor. With the QSAR + in vitro parameterization, 41% of the predictions were within a 10-fold factor and with the calibrated model parameters, 66% were within a 10-fold factor. Amongst the *ab initio* parameterisations A, B and C, the median fold deviation is smallest with the QSAR + in vitro parameterization (15-fold).

Interspecies relative concentration factors

Predictions for continuous 100-day oral administration of 1 mg/kg/day of each compound are shown in Figures 1 to 4 (human), and in Figures 5 to 8 (rat) in Appendix 2.

Steady -state, here defined as 95% of the maximum predicted value, is not always achieved after 100 days of continuous exposure (see Table 15 and Figures 1 to 8 in Appendix 2). The QSAR parameterization (A) does not achieve steady-state at 100 days in rats and even at 2000 days (over five years) in humans for dienestrol, imazalil, cyproconazole, and triadimefon. The in vivo parameterization (D) does not reach steady state after 2000 days in humans for cyproconazole.

Table 15: Compounds for which steady state is not achieved after 100 days or 2000 days continuous exposure, in humans and in rats

	Human		Rat	
	100 days	2000 days	100 days	2000 days
A QSAR only	flutamide, linuron, dienestrol, imazalil, thiaclopid, cyproconazole, triadimefon	dienestrol, imazalil, cyproconazole, triadimefon	dienestrol, imazalil, cyproconazole, triadimefon	-
B htk	imazalil	-	-	-
C QSAR + in vitro	dienestrol	-	-	-
D in vivo	cyproconazole	cyproconazole		-

The human to rat blood concentration ratios after 2000 days continuous exposure are represented in Figure 16. With the QSAR parameterization, the ratio ranges from 1.3 (imazalil, not at steady state in humans) to 4.2 (flutamide); with the htk parameterization it ranges from 0.043 (triadimefon) to 257 (imazalil); with the QSAR + in vitro parameterization, the ratio ranges from 0.56 (linuron) to 5.5 (dienestrol) and with the in vivo parameterization, the ratio ranges from 1 (linuron) to 2169 (cyproconazole, not at steady state in humans). The width of the prediction intervals are relatively invariant on parameterisations and compounds. The predicted ratios are relatively consistent between parameterizations for valproic acid, flutamide, and clothianidin; they vary by over ten-fold for imazalil, triadimefon and cyproconazole.

Figure 16: Human to rat blood concentration ratios (with 95% prediction interval) after 2000 days continuous exposure. A) QSAR parameters, B) httk parameters, C) QSAR + in vitro parameters D) in vivo parameterisation.

Relative Concentration Factors between chemicals

Relative concentrations in human blood following a chronic 2000 days exposure of the nine chemicals belonging to three cumulative assessment groups are reported in Figure 17, according to the four different parameterisations.

Figure 17 : Predicted arterial blood concentrations after 2000 days continuous exposure to 1mg/kg/day in humans in each cumulative assessment group using QSAR, httk, QSAR + in vitro and in vivo parameterisations.

Kinetic absorption factors

The default assumption in MCRA considers that the internal concentration at the target organ is equivalent to the daily exposure per unit of bodyweight. This is defined as a kinetic absorption factor equal to 1. The kinetic absorption factor is proposed as the ratio of the mean concentration at target organ divided by the exposure per unit of bodyweight and per day.

The assumption of a kinetic absorption factor equal to 1 can be met in a variety of situations, for example, with oral exposure, if the chemical is totally absorbed, uniformly distributed in the body, and that, in acute exposures, it is not eliminated, or that in chronic risk assessment, it does not accumulate. A variety of other scenarios could be imagined that result in a “kinetic absorption factor”: less absorption but with bioconcentration at the target organ, total absorption, high affinity for the target organ but with elimination compensating for that higher affinity.

The kinetic model allows risk assessors to refine the default assumption by using the predicted internal concentrations. The values reported in Figure 18 are obtained using liver concentrations over 100 days exposure to a continuous exposure.

Figure 18: Kinetic absorption factors in humans resulting from a 100-day continuous exposures in each cumulative assessment group using QSAR, htk and QSAR + in vitro parameterisations, calculated as a ratio of the mean hepatic concentration over 100 days over the daily exposure per unit bodyweight. 1 is the default value in the Euromix Toolbox.

DISCUSSION

The quality of prediction with the various parameterisations was variable. Results obtained with parameterisation D, in which a small number of parameters were calibrated to fit *in vivo* data for flutamide, clothianidin, imazalil and valproic acid), were, as expected, in better agreement with the data than the *ab initio* parameterisations A, B and C. However, calibrating parameters is time-consuming, and requires large amounts of *in vivo* data for the model to be predictive in dose-to-dose extrapolation. Under the perspective of providing PBPK models for a large number of substances, *ab initio* models that rely upon existing databases or simple QSAR models are more feasible. With the human model, predictions were best with the htkk parameterisation due to the large number of redundant points representing quantity of imazalil excreted in urine, which was best predicted when the GFR was used as an elimination clearance. With the rat model, where a larger number of compounds were tested, predictions were best with the QSAR + *in vitro* parameterisation. For flutamide, valproic acid, and imazalil, kinetics of the parent compound were available in the literature. For imazalil, using the parameters extracted from htkk considerably improved predictions of urinary quantities by increasing the urinary elimination clearance of 2 orders of magnitude, simply using the glomerular filtration rate instead of the QSAR estimate. Flutamide concentrations in the dataset from Radwanski et al. (humans) and in Zuo et al. (rats) were better predicted with htkk or QSAR+ *in vitro* parameterisations due to *in vitro* hepatic clearances which were over 2 orders of magnitude higher than the QSAR estimates. The improvement in predicted triadimefon concentrations in rats with the QSAR + *in vitro* parameterisations were also likely due to higher *in vitro* hepatic clearance compared to the QSAR estimate. However, even with *in vitro* estimates, the internal concentrations were overestimated. Since flutamide is reported to be mainly metabolised rather than excreted as a parent compound [42], the metabolic clearance may have been underestimated.

The use of default values for the intestinal absorption rate (1 h^{-1}) and fraction absorbed (100%) may be responsible for lack of accuracy of the predicted internal concentrations. Indeed, in particular in non-pharmaceutical compounds, the fraction absorbed, observed *in vivo*, is often lower than 100% and large variations in intestinal absorption rate [56]. In the most recent version of htkk, the default value for k_{Gut} is 2.18 h^{-1} .

Application of the COSMOS PBPK model for several chemicals in the perspective of performing quantitative IVIVE in cumulative risk assessment brought up several methodological issues.

The kinetic model implemented in the Euromix Toolbox includes three major exposure routes in order to model dermal, oral, and pulmonary exposures and can therefore be applied to a variety of chemicals and exposure scenarios.

Detailed modelling requires detailed data which is not always available. For example, within the nine selected chemicals, several *ab initio* sets of parameters were available in existing databases or could be calculated with existing QSAR models. However, some chemical-specific parameters, namely the intestinal absorption rate and absorbed fraction, were set to a default value for all chemicals. The tools must therefore compromise between data availability and model complexity. This means that

for lower-tier calculations applicable to many substances (as needed in EuroMix, where we may have cumulative assessment groups of up to 100 substances) we need very simple kinetic models. Therefore, when the PBPK model predicts internal concentrations that are proportional to the external dose, the model can be summarized by a concentration factor.

Relative internal concentration factors between rat and human in the case of continuous exposures leading to an internal steady state were derived. Arterial blood was chosen as it is an important biomarker of exposure and because *in vivo* data on kinetics in humans is often only available in this compartment. This is therefore the tissue with the least uncertainty on PBPK predictions. The interspecies relative internal concentration factors were estimated by simulating continuous exposures, but, in the case of single or repeated boluses, relative internal concentration factors can also be derived on the basis of the characteristic of kinetics (e.g. peak concentration or Area Under the Curve (AUC) at target organ) depending on which is the most relevant in toxicological risk assessment.

The relative internal concentration factors that were derived between compounds belonging to the same cumulative risk assessment group can be used to convert internal RPFs obtained *in vitro* into external RPFs in humans.

In this paper, the relative internal concentration factors were obtained by simulating continuous exposures which resulted in steady states in the target organ. Since the PBPK models are linear, meaning that the internal concentrations are proportional to the external dose at steady state, these factors can be used whatever the dose levels investigated, both for interspecies extrapolation and for chemical RPFs. The external doses which will be estimated based on internal doses are doses per unit of time, not single or repeated doses.

In practice, exposures are often time-dependent and the internal concentrations therefore fluctuate as well. Even in the simplest case of two chemicals present in the environment or food at a constant ratio, if the exposure is non-constant and the two chemicals present differences in internal kinetics, not only with the internal concentrations be time-dependent, but furthermore, the internal concentration ratio will be time-dependent. In this case, the internal relative potency may not be directly converted into an external RPF. This is of particular concern when at least one of the chemicals is absorbed and eliminated fast. In this case, internal concentration factors determined at steady state are no longer valid. In case of an acute simultaneous exposure for example, if the response at the cell level is immediate, the difference in time of peak concentration may imply that once one chemical has reached the tissue, the other may have been cleared: predicting the response based on an addition of both peak concentrations would be a conservative, though simplistic, solution. Even if the PBTK model is used to predict responses at given timepoint, predicting responses, i.e. toxicodynamics, in these circumstances relies on assumptions such as concentration addition and absence of any carry-over effect [57]. Carry-over effects from one chemical to another occur when one compound has a lasting effect on the response to the other chemical, although it has been cleared from the target tissue.

The integration of the time-scale is not only an important issue in cumulative risk assessment: Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) also often include an implicit time-scale which depends on the level (molecular, cellular, tissue, or whole-body) at which each key event occur, [58]. Considering

dose-time response data and delayed effects appears to be an important issue for used of AOPs in risk assessment.

Estimation of the uncertainty of predictions, taking into account model uncertainty, parameter uncertainty, and also population variability which has not been addressed here, are important especially in a risk assessment context. Monte Carlo simulations of both uncertainty and variability should be easy to perform inside the toolbox and fast. The COSMOS model is relatively simple and implemented in C, a compiled, and therefore relatively fast, programming language. Of course, in some cases, it is a bonus for higher-tier calculations if more complex models are also available. For Cypermethrin for example, precise simulations require diffusion-limited models, which is a complexification of all the flow-limited model implemented in the Euromix Toolbox: simpler models will imply sacrifices on precision and accuracy of the predictions. In the structure of the chosen implementation, it is easy to specify and link additional more complex kinetic models to the EuroMix data and model platform.

CONCLUSION

Various *ab initio* parameterisations of the PBTK model included in the Euromix toolbox have been tested on nine substances belonging to three cumulative assessment groups. Intestinal absorption rates, fraction absorbed, and elimination rates, either specifically as hepatic clearances, or more generally as elimination from blood, were of special concern. Indeed, default values were used for the two intestinal absorption parameters although there is evidence that large differences exist between compounds. *In silico* or *in vitro* estimates were not available. The metabolic clearances were in some cases underestimated, either due to limitations of the *in vitro* assays or because metabolism may occur at sites other than the liver. Regarding oral absorption and total clearance, either input from *in vivo* data analysis or calibration of the model parameters with *in vivo* data would likely improve the quality of predictions, but it is a resource intensive, time-consuming task.

When associated with *in vitro* dose-response data, the PBTK model can provide either interspecies or inter-chemical potency factors at steady state, which is relevant in particular for chronic risk assessment. Uncertainty factors can however be large, covering several orders of magnitude.

The PBPK models developed have been implemented in MCRA to convert external exposure to organ-level exposure and to extrapolate *in vitro* exposures to *in vivo* quantitatively (QIVIVE module). The models implemented can be used in data-poor situations, so that calculations can be done for large numbers of chemicals.

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FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the “COSMOS” PBPK model implemented in the MCRA platform.

Figure 2 :Percent of unchanged dienestrol (mean+/-SD) is fitted in order to determine k (elimination rate constant)

Figure 3: Rat hepatocytes ; A, Reaction progress curves of total metabolites apparition at 5 differents concentration versus time. B, a Michaelis-Menten plot of imazalil metabolites initial velocity versus substrate (imazalil) concentration

Figure 4: Human hepatocytes ; A, Reaction progress curves of total metabolites apparition at 5 differents concentrations versus time. B, a Michaelis-Menten plot of imazalil metabolites initial velocity versus substrate (imazalil) concentration

Figure 5: Rat hepatocytes ; A, Reaction progress curves of total metabolites apparition at 5 differents concentration versus time. B, a Michaelis-Menten plot of linuron metabolites initial velocity versus substrate (imazalil) concentration

Figure 6: Human hepatocytes ; A, Reaction progress curves of total metabolites apparition at 5 differents concentration versus time. B, a Michaelis-Menten plot of linuron metabolites initial velocity versus substrate (imazalil) concentration

Figure 7: Contribution of the three metabolic pathways of flutamide in humans (A) and in rats (B) as a function of the flutamide concentration in liver divided by the blood:liver partition coefficient, which represents the concentration that is available in the liver for metabolism, or venous blood in the liver.

Figure 8: Schema for human flutamide metabolism; Liver CYP1A2 metabolizes flutamide into flutamide hydroxide, main metabolite. Deacetylation of flutamide by carboxylesterase generates Flu-1. Reduction of aromatic nitro group into amino group by cytochrome reductase results in conversion of Flutamide to FLU-6.

Figure 11: Case with identical relationship in animals and humans. Circles: unknown quantities; Squares: known quantities. Black arrows: causal relationships (or models); Double lines: equality assumptions; Red arrows: information flow. The shortest path should be taken.

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Figure 9: Distribution of a selection of chemical-specific parameters for flutamide in humans with the httk parameterisation. Estimates for these parameters were the following: $\log_{PCFat}=4.02$, $CLH=531L/h$, $fub=0.376$, $Frac=1$, $kGut=11/h$, $Ke=7.5L/h$

Figure 12: Predicted vs. observed plasmatic concentrations (Flutamide and VPA) or cumulated amounts excreted in urine (Imazalil, μmol) in humans. Black= A) QSAR parameterization, red= B) httk parameterization, green= C) QSAR + in vitro parameterization, blue = D) in vivo parameterisation.

Figure 13: Predicted vs. observed concentrations in rats for flutamide, triadimefon, and VPA. A) QSAR parameters, B) httk parameters, C) QSAR + in vitro parameters, D) in vivo parameterisation.

Figure 14: Predicted vs. observed concentrations in rats for thiacloprid administered in 1, 5, and 100mg/kg BW single oral doses, 1mg/kg BW /day repeated oral doses, or 1mg/kg single IV dose.. Grey lines are used to show that the observations represent the parent compound and metabolites and that the parent compound concentrations are actually equal or smaller than the data points reported. A) QSAR parameters, B) httk parameters, C) QSAR + in vitro parameters, D) in vivo parameterisation.

Figure 15: Predicted vs. observed concentrations in rats for clothianidin administered in 2.5, 5, and 250 mg/kg BW single oral doses and 25 mg/kg BW /day repeated oral doses, and for cyproconazole administered in 10 and 130 mg/kg single oral doses, 10mg/kg BW single IV doses, 0.5mg/kg BW/day repeated oral doses. Grey lines are used to show that the observed concentrations of the parent compound are equal or smaller than the data points reported. A) QSAR parameters, B) httk parameters, C) QSAR + in vitro parameters D) in vivo parameterisation.

Figure 2: **httk** parameterisation predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure to 1mg/kg/day in **humans**. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions

Figure 1: **QSAR** parameterization predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure of **humans** to 1mg/kg/day. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions.

Figure 3: **QSAR + in vitro** parameterization predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure of **humans** to 1mg/kg/day. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions

Figure 17 : Predicted arterial blood concentrations after 2000 days continuous exposure to 1mg/kg/day in humans in each cumulative assessment group using QSAR, httk, QSAR + in vitro and in vivo parameterisations.

Figure 18: Kinetic absorption factors in humans resulting from a 100-day continuous exposures in each cumulative assessment group using QSAR, httk and QSAR + in vitro parameterisations, calculated as a ratio of the mean hepatic concentration over 100 days over the daily exposure per unit bodyweight. 1 is the default value in the Euromix Toolbox.

APPENDIX 1: Parameter distributions in the PBPK model adapted for

Table 1: Flutamide chemical and biochemical specific parameter values and its statistical distributions. LN: LOG NORMAL LN(a,b) means a = ln(mean) and b=sd in ln space

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions	References
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				
Liver /Plasma	PCLiver		LN (5.57, 1.5)	a
Lung /Plasma	PCLung		LN (1.65, 1.1)	a
Kidney /Plasma	PCKidney	-	LN (2.63, 1.5)	a
Fat/Plasma	PCFat	-	LN (2.78, 1.1)	a
gonads/Plasma	PCGonad	-	LN (1.7, 1.5)	a
prostate/Plasma	PCProstate	-	LN (2.17, 1.1)	a
Richly perfused/Plasma	PCRich	-	LN (xx, 1.5)	a
Poorly perfused/Plasma	PCPoor	-	LN (xx, 1.5)	a
Liver/ Plasma (FLU-OH)	PCLiver	-	LN (5.57, 1.5)	a
<i>Absorption and elimination parameters</i>				
Unbound fraction in plasma (Flutamide)	fup	-	0.09	[34]
Unbound fraction in plasma (Flu-OH)	fup	-	0.05	[35]
Oral absorption rate	kgut	1/h	LN (0.64, 1.1)	a
Elimination rate	kurine	L/h	LN (1.25, 1.5)	optimized
Elimination rate (FLU-OH)	kurineM1	L/h	LN (1.85, 1.5)	optimized
Metabolic parameters for human				
Flu to Flu-OH maximum reaction value	VmaxlivM1_invitro	µg/min/mg MSP	LN (0.079,1.1) ^b	[59]

Conc. at half maximum value	KmliverM1	mg/L	1.113	[59]
Flu to Flu-6 maximum reaction value	VmaxlivM2_invitro	µg/min/mg MSP	LN (0.052, 1.1) ^b	[60]
Conc. at half maximum value	KmliverM2	mg/L	23.754	[60]
Flu to Flu-1 maximum reaction value	VmaxlivM3_invitro	µg/min/mg MSP	LN (0.31, 1.1) ^b	[61]
Conc. at half maximum value	KmliverM3	mg/L	82.863	[61]
Total hepatic clearance	CL_H	L/hr	4469.45	Calculated
Metabolic parameters for rat				
Unbound fraction in plasma	fu	-	LN (0.4, 1.5)	[34]
Flu metabolism in liver	VmaxlivM1_inviro	µg/min/mg MSP	LN (0.8, 1.2) ^b	[61]
Conc. at half maximum value	KmliverM1	g/L	0.276	[61]
Flu metabolism in kidney	VmaxkidM1_invitro	µg/min/mg MSP	LN (0.75, 1.1) ^b	[61]
Conc. at half maximum value	KmkidneyM1	g/L	1.6	[61]
Flutamide metabolism in lung	VmaxlungM1_invitro	µg/min/mg MSP	LN (0.028, 1.1) ^b	[61]
Conc. at half maximum value	KmlungM1	g/L	0.193	[61]
Oral absorption rate	kgut	1/h	LN (0.64, 1.1) ^a	optimized
Renal clearance	Cl _R	L/h	LN (0.07, 1.5) ^c	optimized

a: In vivo data of [31] using first order absorption rate constant or AUC ratio for PC.

b; parameters are scaled to whole body species prior to use in model

c Rat glomeration filtration rate was considered

Table 2: Linuron specific parameter values or statistical distributions

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions	References
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				-
fractional unbound	fup	-	1	
live plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver	-	LN(4.42, 1.5)	c
Brain plasma Partition coefficient	PCBrain	-	LN(7.0, 1.1)	c
kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCKidney	-	LN(2.71, 1.1)	c
fat plasm partition coefficient	PCFat	-	LN(81.1, 1.1)	c
gonads plasma partition coefficient	PCGonad	-	LN(3.01, 1.1)	c
restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody	-	LN(4.42, 1.5)	b
Richly perfused/Plasma	PCRich	-	LN (XX, 1.5)	
Poorly perfused/Plasma	PCPoor	-	LN (xx, 1.5)	
Absorption rate constant	kgut	/hr	LN(1, 1.5)	
Maximum reaction value	VmaxlivM1_invitro	nmol/min/10 ⁶ cells	LN (0.03,1.1) ^b	In vitro [59]
Conc. at half maximum value	KmliverM1	Micromole	6.63	In vitro [59]
Total hepatic clearance	CL _H	L/hr	57.4696833	Calculated
Total clearance	kurine*	L/hr	LN(7.62, 1.5)	c
parameters for rat				
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				-
fractional unbound	fup	-	1	
live plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver	-	LN(4.42, 1.5)	c

Brain plasma Partition coefficient	PCBrain	-	LN(7.0, 1.1)	c
kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCKidney	-	LN(2.71, 1.1)	c
fat plasm partition coefficient	PCFat	-	LN(81.1, 1.1)	c
gonads plasma partition coefficient	PCGonad	-	LN(3.01, 1.1)	c
restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody	-	LN(4.42, 1.5)	b
Richly perfused/Plasma	PCRich	-	LN (XX, 1.5)	
Poorly perfused/Plasma	PCPoor	-	LN (xx, 15)	
Absorption rate constant	kgut	/hr	LN(1, 1.5)	
Maximum reaction value	VmaxlivM1_invitro	nmol/min/10 ⁶ cells	LN (0.01,1.1) ^b	In vitro [59]
Conc. at half maximum value	KmliverM1	Micromole	9.98	In vitro [59]
Total hepatic clearance	CL _H	L/hr	0.08	Calculated
Total clearance	kurine	L/hr	LN(0.201, 1.5)	c

b = rest of the body Partition coefficient are set equal to liver

c = parameter are estimated based on QSAR approach and htkk package from R

***scaled from rat Ke value using factor (BMhuman/BMrat)^{0.75}**

Table 3: Dienestrol specific parameter values or statistical distributions

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions	References
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				-
fractional unbound	fup	-	LN(0.6, 1.1)	
live plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver	-	LN(10.11, 1.5)	c
Brain plasma Patition coefficient	PCBrain	-	LN(16.14, 1.1)	c
kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCKidney	-	LN(6.14, 1.1)	c
fat plasm partition coefficient	PCFat	-	LN(188, 1.1)	c
gonads plasma partition coefficient	PCGonad	-	LN(3.45, 1.1)	c
restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody	-	LN(10.11, 1.5)	b
Richly perfused/Plasma	PCRich	-	LN (XX, 1.5)	-
Poorly perfused/Plasma	PCPoor	-	LN (xx, 15)	-
Absorption rate constant	kgut	/h	LN(1, 1.5)	
Total hepatic clearance	CL_H	L/hr	283	In vitro [59]
Total clearance	K_{urine}*	L/hr	LN(9.48, 1.5)	c
parameters for rat				
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				-
fractional unbound	fup	-	LN(0.6, 1.1)	
live plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver	-	LN(10.11, 1.5)	c
Brain plasma Patition coefficient	PCBrain	-	LN(16.14, 1.1)	c

kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCKidney	-	LN(6.14, 1.1)	c
fat plasm partition coefficient	PCFat	-	LN(188, 1.1)	c
gonads plasma partition coefficient	PCGonad	-	LN(3.45, 1.1)	c
restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody	-	LN(10.11, 1.5)	b
Richly perfused/Plasma	PCRich	-	LN (XX, 1.5)	-
Poorly perfused/Plasma	PCPoor	-	LN (xx, 15)	-
Absorption rate constant	kgut	/h	LN(1, 1.5)	
Total hepatic clearance	CL _H	L/hr	3	In vitro [59]
Total clearance	K _{urine}	L/hr	LN(0.25, 1.5)	c

b = rest of the body Partition coefficient are set equal to liver

c = parameter are estimated based on QSAR approach and htk package from R

***scaled from rat Ke value using factor (BMhuman/BMrat)^{0.75}**

Table 4: Clothianidin specific parameter values or statistical distributions

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions	References
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				
fractional unbound	fup	-	1	-
live plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver	-	LN(1.78, 1.5)	a
Brain plasma Partition coefficient	PCBrain	-	LN(0.2, 1.1)	a
kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCKidney	-	LN(1.80, 1.1)	a
fat plasm partition coefficient	PCFat	-	LN(0.39, 1.1)	a
gonads plasma partition coefficient	PCGonad	-	LN(0.86, 1.1)	a
restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody	-	LN(1.78, 1.5)	b
<i>Absorption and elimination parameters</i>				
Absorption rat constant	kgut	/h	LN(1, 1.5)	
Total clearence	Kurine*	L/hr	LN(2.27, 1.5)	a
parameters for rat				
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				
fractional unbound	fup	-	1	-
live plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver	-	LN(1.78, 1.5)	a
Brain plasma Partition coefficient	PCBrain	-	LN(0.2, 1.1)	a
kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCKidney	-	LN(1.80, 1.1)	a

fat plasm partition coefficient	PCFat	-	LN(0.39, 1.1)	a
gonads plasma partition coefficient	PCGonad	-	LN(0.86, 1.1)	a
restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody	-	LN(1.78, 1.5)	b
<i>Absorption and elimination parameters</i>				
Absorption rat constant	kgut	/h	LN(1, 1.5)	
Total clearance	kurine	L/hr	LN(0.06, 1.5)	a

*scaled from rat Ke value using factor $(BM_{human}/BM_{rat})^{0.75}$

Table 5: Thiacloprid specific parameter values or statistical distributions

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions	References
Partition coefficients				-
fractional unbound	fup		1	
live plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver		LN(2.60, 1.5)	a
Brain plasma Patition coefficient	PCBrain		LN(0.67, 1.1)	a
kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCKidney		LN(1.67, 1.1)	a
fat plasm partition coefficient	PCFat		LN(1.23, 1.1)	a
gonads plasma partition coefficient	PCGonad		LN(0.51, 1.1)	a
restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody		LN(2.60, 1.5)	b
Richly perfused/Plasma	PCRich	-	LN (XX, 1.5)	-
Poorly perfused/Plasma	PCPoor	-	LN (xx, 15)	-
Absorption rat constant	kgut	/h	LN(1, 1.5)	
Total clearence	Kurine*	L/hr	LN(2.27, 1.5)	a
Rat parameters				
Partition coefficients			-	
fractional unbound	fup		1	
live plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver		LN(2.60, 1.5)	a
Brain plasma Patition coefficient	PCBrain		LN(0.67, 1.1)	a
kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCKidney		LN(1.67, 1.1)	a
fat plasm partition coefficient	PCFat		LN(1.23, 1.1)	a
gonads plasma partition coefficient	PCGonad		LN(0.51, 1.1)	a
restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody		LN(2.60, 1.5)	b
Richly perfused/Plasma	PCRich	-	LN (XX, 1.5)	-

Poorly perfused/Plasma	PCPoor	-	LN (xx, 15)	-
Absorption rat constant	kgut	/h	LN(1, 1.5)	
Total clearance	Kurine*	L/hr	LN(0.060, 1.5)	a

a = partition coefficient are estimated based on AUC method from rat in-vivo studies and total clearance is visually fitted against in-vivo data

***scaled from rat Ke value using factor $(BM_{human}/BM_{rat})^{0.75}$**

Table 6: Kinetic parameters for for Triadimefon and Triadimenol

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values	References
<i>Triadimefon Partition coefficients</i>				
Liver plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver		1.25	(Crowell et al., 2011)
Brain Plasma partition coefficient	PCBrain		0.97	(Crowell et al., 2011)
Kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCKidney		1.32	(Crowell et al., 2011)
Fat plasm partition coefficient	PCFat		13.47	(Crowell et al., 2011)
Restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody		1.32	(Crowell et al., 2011)
<i>Triadimenol Partition coefficients</i>				
Live plasma partition coefficient	PCLiver		6.98	(Crowell et al., 2011)
Kidney plasma partition coefficient	PCBrain		2.76	(Crowell et al., 2011)
Fat plasm partition coefficient	PCKidney		4.54	(Crowell et al., 2011)
Brain Plasma partition coefficient	PCFat		1.18	(Crowell et al., 2011)
Restbody plasma partition coefficient	PCRestBody		2.76	(Crowell et al., 2011)
Metabolic parameter for Triadimefon				
Triadimefon reduction to Triadimenol	Vmax	$\mu\text{mole /h/kg}^{.75}$	556.4	(Crowell et al., 2010)
Triadimefon reduction to Triadimenol	Km	$\mu\text{mole /L}$	47.3	(Crowell et al., 2010)
Triadimenol oxidation to Triadimefon	Vmax	$\mu\text{mole /h/kg}^{.75}$	278.2	(Crowell et al., 2010)
Triadimenol oxidation to Triadimefon	Km	$\mu\text{mole /L}$	31.5	(Crowell et al., 2010)

Table 7: Imazalil-specific parameter values or statistical distributions used for rats.

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions ^a	References
Molecular Mass	<i>MM</i>	g/mole	297.18	(pearce et al. 2017)
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				
Blood / air	<i>PCAir</i>	-	10 ⁹⁹	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Fat / blood	<i>PCFat</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (36.5, 3)	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Liver / blood	<i>PCLiver</i>	-	2	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Poorly perfused / blood	<i>PCPoor</i>	-	0.64	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Richly perfused / blood	<i>PCRich</i>	-	2	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Viable skin / blood	<i>PCSkin</i>	-	0.64	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Viable skin / stratum corneum	<i>PCSkin_sc</i>	-	0.0175	^{b,c}
Unbound fraction in blood	<i>fub</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.036 1.5)	(pearce et al. 2017)
Fraction absorbed by gut	<i>Frac</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.8 , 1.2)	(pearce et al. 2017)
Oral absorption rate	<i>kGut</i>	1/h	<i>LN</i> (1, 1.5)	(pearce et al. 2017)
Renal excretion rate	<i>Ke</i>	L/h	<i>LN</i> (0.09, 1.5)	- ^e
Metabolic clearance	<i>CLH</i>	L/h	<i>LN</i> (6, 1.5)	(pearce et al. 2017)
Skin diffusion coefficient	<i>Kp_sc_vs</i>	dm/h	<i>LN</i> (0.00002, 1.5)	- ^d

^a *LN*: log-normal distribution (geometric mean, geometric SD); *U*: uniform distribution (lower bound, upper bound).

^b These value are baseline vales, scaled to *PCFat* during the simulations, see text.

^c This value was estimated by diving *PCSkin* by *PCFat*.

^d Value adjusted to fit the human data.

^e Set to the glomerular filtration rate.

Table 8: Imazalil-specific parameter values or statistical distributions used for humans.

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions ^a	References
Molecular Mass	<i>MM</i>	g/mole	297.18	(pearce et al. 2017)
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				
Blood / air	<i>PCAir</i>	-	10 ⁹⁹	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Fat / blood	<i>PCFat</i>	-	LN (36.5, 3)	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Liver / blood	<i>PCLiver</i>	-	2	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Poorly perfused / blood	<i>PCPoor</i>	-	0.64	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Richly perfused / blood	<i>PCRich</i>	-	2	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Viable skin / blood	<i>PCSkin</i>	-	0.64	(Valentin, 2002) ^b
Viable skin / stratum corneum	<i>PCSkin_sc</i>		0.0175	^{b,c}
Unbound fraction in blood	<i>fub</i>	-	LN (0.015, 1.5)	(pearce et al. 2017) ^d
Fraction absorbed by gut	<i>Frac</i>	-	LN (0.8, 1.2)	- ^d
Oral absorption rate	<i>kGut</i>	1/h	LN (10, 1.5)	- ^d
Renal excretion rate	<i>Ke</i>	L/h	LN (17, 1.5)	- ^d
Metabolic clearance	<i>CLH</i>	L/h	LN (50, 1.5)	- ^d
Skin diffusion coefficient	<i>Kp_sc_vs</i>	dm/h	LN(0.00002, 1.5)	- ^d

^a LN: log-normal distribution (geometric mean, geometric SD); U: uniform distribution (lower bound, upper bound).

^b These values are baseline values, scaled to *PCFat* during the simulations, see text.

^c This value was estimated by dividing *PCSkin* by *PCFat*.

^d Value adjusted to fit the data (see text and Table 5).

Table 9: Cyproconazole-specific parameter values or statistical distributions used for rats.

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions ^a	References
Molecular Mass	<i>MM</i>	g/mole	291.78	-
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				
Blood / air	<i>PCAir</i>	-	10 ⁹⁹	(Peyret et al., 2010)
Fat / blood	<i>PCFat</i>	-	LN (7.1, 3)	(Peyret et al., 2010)
Liver / blood	<i>PCLiver</i>	-	0.4	(Peyret et al., 2010) ^b
Poorly perfused / blood	<i>PCPoor</i>	-	0.2	(Peyret et al., 2010) ^b
Richly perfused / blood	<i>PCRich</i>	-	0.4	(Peyret et al., 2010) ^b
Viable skin / blood	<i>PCSkin</i>	-	0.2	(Peyret et al., 2010) ^b
Viable skin / stratum corneum	<i>PCSkin_sc</i>	-	0.028	^{b,c}
Unbound fraction in blood	<i>fup</i>	-	LN (0.11 1.5)	(Pearce et al. 2017)
Fraction absorbed by gut	<i>Frac</i>	-	LN (0.996 , 1.5)	(Pearce et al. 2017)
Oral absorption rate	<i>kGut</i>	1/h	LN (1, 1.5)	(Pearce et al. 2017)
Renal excretion rate	<i>Ke</i>	L/h	0	- ^e
Metabolic clearance	<i>CLH</i>	L/h	LN (0.21, 1.5)	(Pearce et al. 2017)
Skin diffusion coefficient	<i>Kp_sc_vs</i>	dm/h	LN (0.1, 2.0)	- ^e

^a LN: log-normal distribution (geometric mean, geometric SD); U: uniform distribution (lower bound, upper bound).

^b These value are baseline vales, scaled to *PCFat* during the simulations, see text.

^c This value was estimated by diving *PCSkin* by *PCFat*.

^d Value adjusted to fit the data.

^e Arbitrary value.

Table 10: Cyproconazole-specific parameter values or statistical distributions used for humans.

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions ^a	References
Molecular Mass	<i>MM</i>	g/mole	291.78	-
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				
Blood / air	<i>PCAir</i>	-	10 ⁹⁹	(Peyret et al., 2010)
Fat / blood	<i>PCFat</i>	-	LN (7.1, 3)	(Peyret et al., 2010)
Liver / blood	<i>PCLiver</i>	-	0.4	(Peyret et al., 2010) ^b
Poorly perfused / blood	<i>PCPoor</i>	-	0.2	(Peyret et al., 2010) ^b
Richly perfused / blood	<i>PCRich</i>	-	0.4	(Peyret et al., 2010) ^b
Viable skin / blood	<i>PCSkin</i>	-	0.2	(Peyret et al., 2010) ^b
Viable skin / stratum corneum	<i>PCSkin_sc</i>		0.028	^{b,c}
Unbound fraction in blood	<i>fup</i>	-	LN (0.07, 1.5)	(Pearce et al. 2017)
Fraction absorbed by gut	<i>Frac</i>	-	LN (0.996, 1.5)	(Pearce et al. 2017)
Oral absorption rate	<i>kGut</i>	1/h	LN (1, 1.5)	(Pearce et al. 2017)
Renal excretion rate	<i>Ke</i>	L/h	0	- ^e
Metabolic clearance	<i>CLH</i>	L/h	LN (23.4, 1.5)	(Pearce et al. 2017)
Skin diffusion coefficient	<i>Kp_sc_vs</i>	dm/h	LN(0.1, 2)	- ^e

^a LN: log-normal distribution (geometric mean, geometric SD); U: uniform distribution (lower bound, upper bound).

^b These values are baseline values, scaled to *PCFat* during the simulations, see text.

^c This value was estimated by dividing *PCSkin* by *PCFat*.

^d Value adjusted to fit the data.

^e Arbitrary value.

Table 11: Valproic acid-specific parameter values or statistical distributions used for rats.

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions ^a	References
Molecular Mass	<i>MM</i>	g/mole	144.21	-
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				
Blood / air	<i>PCAir</i>	-	10 ⁹⁹	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007)
Fat / blood	<i>PCFat</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.16, 3)	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007)
Liver / blood	<i>PCLiver</i>	-	0.28	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007) ^b
Poorly perfused / blood	<i>PCPoor</i>	-	0.25	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007) ^b
Richly perfused / blood	<i>PCRich</i>	-	0.36	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007) ^b
Viable skin / blood	<i>PCSkin</i>	-	0.25	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007) ^b
Viable skin / stratum corneum	<i>PCSkin_sc</i>	-	1.56	^{b,c}
Unbound fraction in blood	<i>fup</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.50, 1.5)	(Pearce et al., 2017)
Fraction absorbed by gut	<i>Frac</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.996, 1.5)	(Bois et al., 2017)
Oral absorption rate	<i>kGut</i>	1/h	<i>LN</i> (2.88, 1.5)	(Bois et al., 2017)
Renal excretion rate	<i>Ke</i>	L/h	0	- ^e
Metabolic clearance	<i>CLH</i>	L/h	0.4	- ^d
Skin diffusion coefficient	<i>Kp_sc_vs</i>	dm/h	<i>LN</i> (0.1, 2.0)	- ^e

^a *LN*: log-normal distribution (geometric mean, geometric SD); *U*: uniform distribution (lower bound, upper bound).

^b These values are baseline values, scaled to *PCFat* during the simulations, see text.

^c This value was estimated by dividing *PCSkin* by *PCFat*.

^d Value adjusted to fit the data.

^e Arbitrary value.

Table 12: Valproic acid-specific parameter values or statistical distributions used for humans.

Parameters	Symbols	Units	Values or distributions ^a	References
Molecular Mass	<i>MM</i>	g/mole	144.21	-
<i>Partition coefficients</i>				
Blood / air	<i>PCAir</i>	-	10 ⁹⁹	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007)
Fat / blood	<i>PCFat</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.16, 3)	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007)
Liver / blood	<i>PCLiver</i>	-	0.28	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007) ^b
Poorly perfused / blood	<i>PCPoor</i>	-	0.25	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007) ^b
Richly perfused / blood	<i>PCRich</i>	-	0.36	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007) ^b
Viable skin / blood	<i>PCSkin</i>	-	0.25	(Rodgers et al., 2005, 2006, 2007) ^b
Viable skin / stratum corneum	<i>PCSkin_sc</i>		1.56	^{b,c}
Unbound fraction in blood	<i>fup</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.14, 1.5)	(Bois et al., 2017)
Fraction absorbed by gut	<i>Frac</i>	-	<i>LN</i> (0.996, 1.5)	(Bois et al., 2017)
Oral absorption rate	<i>kGut</i>	1/h	<i>LN</i> (2.88, 1.5)	(Bois et al., 2017)
Renal excretion rate	<i>Ke</i>	L/h	0	- ^e
Metabolic clearance	<i>CLH</i>	L/h	<i>LN</i> (8.8, 1.5)	- ^d
Skin diffusion coefficient	<i>Kp_sc_vs</i>	dm/h	<i>LN</i> (0.1, 2)	- ^e

^a *LN*: log-normal distribution (geometric mean, geometric SD); *U*: uniform distribution (lower bound, upper bound).

^b These values are baseline values, scaled to *PCFat* during the simulations, see text.

^c This value was estimated by dividing *PCSkin* by *PCFat*.

^d Value adjusted to fit the data.

^e Arbitrary value.

APPENDIX 2: Simulations of human blood concentrations under continuous 100-day exposure scenarios

Figure 1: QSAR parameterization predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure of humans to 1mg/kg/day. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions.

Figure 2: *httk* parameterisation predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure to 1mg/kg/day in humans. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions

Figure 3: QSAR + *in vitro* parameterization predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure of humans to 1mg/kg/day. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions

Figure 4: *in vivo* parameterization predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure of **humans** to 1mg/kg/day. **Black:** predictions without variability. **Red:** = median MC prediction. **Grey=** 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions

Figure 5: QSAR parameterization predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure of **rats** to 1mg/kg/day. **Black:** predictions without variability. **Red:** = median MC prediction. **Grey=** 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions

Figure 6: *httk* parameterization predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure of rats to 1mg/kg/day. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions

Figure 7: QSAR + *in vitro* parameterization predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure of rats to 1mg/kg/day. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions

Figure 8: *in vivo* parameterization predictions for a continuous 100-day exposure of rats to 1mg/kg/day. Black: predictions without variability. Red: = median MC prediction. Grey= 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of MC predictions